

TEA

The
European Archaeologist

*The newsletter of EAA members for EAA members
Issue 83 – Winter 2025*

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Issue 83 – Winter 2025

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The views expressed are those of the individual authors and do not necessarily represent official EAA policy.

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Do you have something that you would like to contribute to TEA?

We welcome a range of contributions including:

- Letters to the editors
- Opinion or Debate pieces
- Insights
- Short reports
- Project overview articles
- Object biographies
- Book reviews
- Announcements (jobs, field schools, publications, funding opportunities, etc.)
- Meet a Member for *TEA* (suggest someone for us to feature)
- Proposals for *TEA*'s next cover image (enter the TEA Photojournalism competition)
- Something else? Send us an idea!

Please contact *TEA* editors Samantha S. Reiter and Matthew J. Walsh at: tea@e-a-a.org

Cover

Archaeology is art. And science.

João Vincius Chiesa Back

University of Minho & University of Évora

This image simulates a Bronze Age funerary context from the northwest of the Iberian Peninsula. Based on photogrammetry and 3D modeling, the image symbolizes the use of a horizontal rim vessel discovered in a grave at the Quinta do Amorim 2 archaeological site (Braga, Portugal), which was the main focus of my presentation at EAA 2024.

Since the late 19th century and throughout the 20th century, archaeologists have observed traces on the inner walls of this type of vessel, particularly on the side opposite the handle, which they interpreted as possibly being soot and/or organic residues. Recently, studies jointly coordinated by Dr. César Oliveira (Hercules/University of Évora) and Dr. Ana Bettencourt (Lab2PT/University of Minho) have investigated the chemical nature of these residues in well-documented funerary contexts using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). The detailed analysis of these traces demonstrates how closer collaboration with the so-called ‘hard sciences’ can provide crucial insights into the probable contents of these types of vessels, which are characteristic of Bronze Age funerary contexts from Northwest Portugal and Spain.

The present digital drawing of the vessel and the grave, created from plans drawings and based on both 3D modeling and photogrammetry of the vessel, demonstrates the essential link between science and art in archaeology. Whether through analytical chemistry techniques or the use of digital art software, archaeological interpretations clearly highlight – just as the fire likely used in the Bronze Age ritual practices mentioned – how we can further enrich our understanding of the human past.

Just as Leopold von Ranke argued that history is both art and science, and that this dual nature does not diminish its credibility, we hold the same view regarding archaeology. Archaeology is art. And science.

NB: This issue’s cover is graced with a simulation of a horizontal rim vessel from the Bronze Age site of Quinta do Amorim 2 (Portugal).

Letter from the Editors

Dear colleagues,

Happy New Year!

We hope that each of you has had a nice start to 2025, whether this be personally or professionally! First off for this year, we would like to thank everyone who contributed to *TEA*'s photojournalism competition in 2024. Last year, you selected three winning images by popular vote; the first of these (by João Vincíus Chiesa Back) features on this issue's [cover](#). In short, 2024 was a year of interesting articles and fascinating finds and we are grateful to you all for sharing them with us. We look forward to continuing to seek out and help highlight the important work of which so many of *EAA*'s members are a part in this upcoming year as well.

Sadly, 2024 saw a troubling rise in nationalistic and authoritarian ideologies gaining political ground in parts of Europe, in the US, and elsewhere. Many of the ideologies, policies and actions are in opposition to the [EAA's Codes and Principles](#). We urge you to review these and to think and act proactively to implement these principles in your own corners of the world. As students of humanity's complicated past, we have a unique perspective from which to recognise the inherent dangers of unchecked and/or unreflective agendas and the tragedies brought on by racism, intolerance, ignorance, and bigotry. It is our firm belief that by holding ourselves to a high standard of professional principles, as well as individual kindness to others, we can help combat the mindsets of prejudice and sectarianism that are so often the remit of right-wing extremism and nationalist thinking. Even if we do not focus on the human and ecological crises to which many such philosophies eventually lead, the price to cultural heritage and the archaeological record is also often considerable – and permanent.

In the coming year, we encourage each of you to be especially attuned to politics, policies, and practices that threaten to push global society to relive aspects of the past that are better left in the history books. This is not hyperbole, in the first 72 hours of the Trump presidency, his administration [rescinded 72 Executive Orders](#), including Executive Order 14049 'White House Initiative on Advancing Educational Equality, Excellence, and Economic Opportunities for Native Americans and Strengthening Tribal Colleges and Universities', Executive Order 14124 'White House Initiative on Advancing Educational Equity, Excellence, and Economic Opportunity Through Hispanic-Serving Institutions', as well as Executive Order 14031 'Advancing Equity, Justice, and Opportunity for Asian Americans, Native Hawaiians, and Pacific Islanders'. These are actions that will directly hinder Native American, Indigenous Latin Americans, and Native Hawaiian (and other) education and outreach programmes, including many which focus on Indigenous heritage and traditional knowledge, archaeology, and environmental studies. Also rescinded were Executive Order 13988 'Preventing and Combating Discrimination on the Basis of Gender Identity or Sexual Orientation', Executive Order 14075 'Advancing Equality for Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer, and Intersex Individuals' and Executive Order 14021 'Guaranteeing an Educational Environment Free From Discrimination on the Basis of Sex, Including Sexual Orientation or Gender Identity', whilst implementing the Presidential Action '[Defending Women from Gender Ideology Extremism and Restoring Biological Truth to the Federal Government](#)', a set of actions targeting the human rights and freedoms of the LGBTQIA+ community. This is not to mention the rescindment of numerous Orders aimed at protecting and advocating for the education and livelihoods of minorities and other at-risk communities such as

African Americans, Latin Americans, Asian Americans, and Pacific Islanders, which may set a fearful precedent to other parts of the globe, including Europe. The changes may have a powerful negative effect on those who make efforts to highlight global policy for the advancement of science broadly, and addressing the fatal impact of climate and environmental crises we currently face, including on the cultural heritage. These are just a selection of actions highlighting subjects traditionally dear to archaeological study. We encourage you to follow the included links to learn more for yourself and to continue to follow situations as they develop both in Europe and elsewhere. Every person makes choices as they can; we urge you as colleagues and friends to use the tools and knowledge that you have to try to shed some light in what appear to be some dark times approaching.

On a lighter note (pun intended), it was delightful to see so many of you in Rome for the 30th Annual Meeting! Perhaps unsurprisingly, The Eternal City was a remarkable place to spend a few late summer days catching up with colleagues, making new friends, and engaging with the most recent advances in archaeological research and scholarship. As you can read in the [EAA Secretariat's report](#) and the [results of the EAA's Annual Survey](#), the Rome AM had an astounding 5172 participants, making it by far the busiest AM in the EAA's history to date! We of course thank the many dedicated organisers and facility staff, but we wish to express a special thanks to the many student and early career volunteers that made such a huge meeting possible – thank you for your time, hard work, and help! We are already looking forward to another outstanding AM in Belgrade later this year.

In addition to the [EAA Calendar](#), [In Case You Missed It](#), a Chat with [EAA Vice President Ariane Ballmer](#) and [Meet a Member with Anne Leschallier de Lisle](#), and a Spotlight on the [Community for Climate Change and Heritage](#) this issue contains the above-mentioned AM report as well as the results of the 2024 Annual Evaluation Survey. For research dissemination, we feature Hrvoje Potrebica and colleagues' announcement of a [newly discovered Illyrian helmet](#) and other grave goods from the Zakotorac site in Croatia as well as an article in which Jaun Ochando et al. present new findings on [Neanderthal tar extraction](#) in Gibraltar. Yvonne Shashoua discusses how [archaeologists should come to terms with plastics](#) as an archaeological material. Zeina Khashashneh provides an overview of the [restoration of Bayt Al Jaghbeer](#) house in As-Salt, Jordan as a means of education and youth outreach. Similarly, Prince Kondeh and Megan Crutcher provide a glimpse of how the [Kru Coast Heritage Initiative in Liberia](#) is educating youth and highlighting community-based historical archaeology.

Finally, the EAA mourns the loss of three of our own, [Françoise Audouze](#), [Colin Renfrew](#) and John Barrett, each of whom played pivotal roles in the Association in various capacities. Our condolences go out to their families, friends, and colleagues, and to all of those who have lost dear ones in this past year.

Though we have lost Members, we honour their memory by standing true and standing together, no matter what 2025 may bring.

Best regards,

Matthew J. Walsh & Samantha S. Reiter

Editors

Calendar for EAA Members

January – May 2025

1 January	Beginning of the 2025 EAA membership
1 January	Deadline for submissions to TEA winter issue
10 January	EAA Executive Board meeting
29 January	Payment deadline (registration and membership fee) for all session organisers
30 January	Final list of sessions and session organisers for the 31st EAA Annual Meeting in Belgrade, Serbia, available
January - February	Call for nominations to the EAA election circulated to Members
January - February	Call for nominations to the European Heritage Prize circulated to Members
January - February	Call for nominations to the Oscar Montelius Foundation (OMF) Early Career Achievement Prize (ECAP) circulated to Members
3 February	Call for volunteers opens
6 February	Deadline for contribution submissions for the 31 st EAA Annual Meeting
28 February	Call for volunteers closes
28 February	Deadline for EAA Book Prize nominations
7- 9 March	EAA Executive Board meeting
10 March	Partial deadline to apply for EAA financial support to EAA Communities
31 March	Deadline for notification of acceptance / rejection to contribution authors
31 March	Deadline for early bird membership fee payment
1 April	Deadline for submissions to TEA spring issue
7 April	Call for grant applications ends
7 April	Deadline for nominations of election candidates by Members
17 April	Announcement of grants allocation
18 - 21 April	EAA Secretariat closed for Easter
24 April	Early Bird Annual Meeting registration fee deadline

April – May	Call for nominations to the EAA Student Award circulated to the Members
1 May	Deadline for nominations to the European Heritage Prize
5 May	Registration and membership payment deadline for presenters (first authors)
15 May	Deadline for registration cancellation without handling fee
30 May	Preliminary version of scientific programme announced at the 31 st EAA Annual Meeting website

In Case You Missed It...

Joana Valdez-Tullett

EAA Social Media Editor

[Archaeologists uncover one of the oldest and most complete wooden tools ever found in Britain](#)

[DNA evidence rewrites history of Pompeii victims buried in volcanic eruption](#)

[Neanderthals were the first fossil collectors, new evidence from Prado Vargas Cave reveals](#)

[Norway Museum repatriates Rapanui Remains to Easter Island](#)

[Viking colonizers of Iceland and nearby Faroe Islands had very different origins, study finds](#)

[Foccacia: a Neolithic culinary tradition dating back 9,000 years ago](#)

[Glen Coe: fresh archaeological discoveries bring new insights into lives of massacred MacDonald clan](#)

[Ritually bent Bronze Age sword recovered in Denmark](#)

[Archaeologists find 7,000-Year-Old Settlement during excavation for new road](#)

EAA Report

From Rome to Belgrade: (Re)view of EAA Annual Meetings

Sylvie Květinová

EAA Secretariat

The 30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome, Italy, held on 28-31 August 2024, was memorable and overwhelming, in many ways. The astounding attendance of 5172 participants (4396 onsite and 776 online) made the event the biggest ever EAA Annual Meeting (Figure 1). This huge attendance revealed some structural challenges embedded in the growth of EAA Annual Meetings, and with the hybrid meeting format that we have pioneered since 2022. John Carman’s debate piece, and EAA President’s response, published in the autumn *TEA* issue no. 82, addressed some of these problems. Members have also told us of other issues in their responses to the EAA annual survey (see below, this issue) and have also kindly emailed the EAA Secretariat with feedback.

Figure 1. EAA Annual Meeting participants

This growing number of attendees, sessions, papers and posters is a positive challenge, inviting new solutions towards continued inclusivity, as Eszter Bánffy wrote in her debate piece. Yet we must address the practicalities. In view of the high figures and the restricted venue capacity in Belgrade, the 2025 Annual Meeting organisers, together with a task force composed of EAA Executive Board and Secretariat members, has prepared a range of measures to control the size of EAA Annual Meetings.

The EAA Executive Board and staff extend sincere apologies to those colleagues whose sessions or presentations suffered from technical shortcomings or who had other negative experiences in Rome. With the Belgrade team, we are currently working to make the 2025 Annual Meeting a positive

experience for everyone. This article summarises the key issues that we face and how we are seeking to address them within the realm of what is possible and practical.

By way of context, the growth of EAA Annual Meetings has one important constraint, and that is the venue capacity. While some host cities are expected to attract many EAA Members (like Rome), other locations are popular quite unpredictably, and it is tricky to match estimates with the lecture rooms and venues available. For reasons of the costs, the EAA usually employs university or other academic premises rather than conference centres for sessions, and the Annual Meeting format is framed by the spaces at hand with all the related implications. While the organising team can be very creative, some facts are a given, such as venue capacity and room distribution, local climate and the presence (or absence) of air-conditioning. It is up to the individual Members whether they decide to attend onsite or online. In view of EAA's policy of rotating its Annual Meetings around Europe while upholding some very basic principles, the conference is largely shaped by local conditions rather than excluding certain countries due to venue particularities.

Virtually every Annual Meeting participant attends to organise a session and/or present an oral and/or poster contribution. In order to facilitate creation of the academic programme, the active participation at the Rome Annual Meeting was limited to organising one session and submitting one oral and one poster contribution as main author, a rule that suited most (77%) delegates. We continue with this practice.

Altogether 535 session proposals were submitted for Rome in November 2023 and were subsequently reduced to 359 sessions presented (see Figure 2 for comparison to previous Annual Meetings). The process of reducing the number of sessions (rejecting an increased number of sessions as well as merging others) was painful to many – the session organisers, the 2024 Scientific Committee, the EAA Executive Board and staff (see the [statement issued by the EAA Executive Board](#)). The final number of parallel sessions in Rome was 65, as compared to 50 in 2023 Belfast and 36 in 2022 Budapest. For Belgrade, altogether 265 session proposals were received and the Scientific Committee accepted 252 sessions, which suggests the 2025 Annual Meeting will be a smaller event comparable to the 2023 Belfast event.

Figure 2. Number of sessions accepted at EAA Annual Meetings

The ratio between papers proposed (4061) and accepted (3719) for the Rome Annual Meeting featured less compression, and there was very little rejection rate in the final number of 416 posters accepted (see Figures 3 and 4 for comparison to previous Annual Meetings). Going forwards, strict quality control must apply across all sessions, papers and posters, and we cannot exceed any venue capacity. The call for contributions for Belgrade ends on 6 February and we are looking forward to receiving your submissions.

Figure 3. Number of papers accepted at EAA Annual Meetings

Figure 4. Number of posters accepted at EAA Annual Meetings

Features that can help attendees maximise their benefits from EAA Annual Meetings is livestreaming of sessions and on-demand availability of session recordings for six months following the Annual

Meeting. This offers delegates the opportunity to watch sessions they have not been able to take part in onsite. Sessions presented at the 30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome are available for on-demand viewing on the EAA 2024 web platform and mobile app until 30 April 2025. Unfortunately, due to both technical issues and the reluctance of session organisers to publish their sessions, only 215 (60%) out of the 535 Rome sessions could finally be made available on demand. For Belgrade, the Annual Meeting website therefore stipulates that by submitting a session proposal, session organisers agree to its recording and availability for on-demand viewing on the EAA conference web platform by registered participants for six months after the Annual Meeting. The same requirement applies to presenters of oral contributions; however, session recordings can, in justified cases, be edited on request.

The aims and rationale for the hybrid format are clear: to increase inclusivity of the EAA Annual Meetings by allowing remote attendance of participants with mobility issues, health concerns, travel or financial restrictions, etc. As a policy, and when it works flawlessly, the hybrid format is perfect. The trouble is that, in practical terms, the hybrid format often suffers from technical problems, thus impacting the onsite programme and offline experience. The technical problems concern mainly the hardware used and support available. The EAA use locally available infrastructure and we employ trained student volunteers to keep the costs down. The conference budget is mostly based on the delegates' registration fees, which we try to keep as low as possible. There is therefore a mismatch between what technology can theoretically offer and what delegates expect on one hand, and what the conference organising team can reasonably afford in view of the available funds. Looking to the future, we aim to enhance provision by hiring additional computers, speakers, microphones, IT technicians, etc., but only to the degree that the conference budget (registration fee) allows.

For sustainability and space reasons, the EAA abandoned printed poster display after Covid. Posters are now available on e-poster boards, in the mobile app and on the EAA website, which suits 42% of the annual survey respondents. However, the exposure and display quality of posters was not ideal in Rome due to their dissociation from sessions and technical problems. For Belgrade, posters will therefore be submitted to sessions in the same way as paper proposals. While due to time constrictions no formal timeslots are reserved for poster presentations within the sessions, session organisers are asked to introduce posters during their discussions and use any last-minute cancellations of papers for presentation of posters. It is hoped that the increased attention dedicated to poster presentations will reduce the ratio of Annual Meeting attendees who declared not being interested in posters (19%) and will convince those who would prefer traditional poster display (25%).

Accompanying social events at Annual Meeting intend to enrich the academic programme and offer opportunities to network and mingle. Local organisers work hard to select the best social events venues and services to show off the city attractions to archaeological participants and often must adapt to strict onsite regulations. The inventive selection and creative use of local sites and services often means that there is no precedent practice to draw from. This may sometime result in an unexpected or negative experience. Since venues and services are contracted long before the Annual Meeting, there may be little space for improvements in real time. However, the lessons learned from the Rome Annual Meeting Opening Ceremony and catering will be shared with the upcoming Annual Meeting organisers to hopefully guarantee better outcomes. The 2025 event will also continue the new (since 2023 Belfast) more inclusive Closing Ceremony rather than the traditional Annual Dinner, accessible to only a few.

We look forward to welcoming you to the 2025 Belgrade Annual Meeting and to helping us to improve our EAA conferences.

Report

EAA 2024 Annual Evaluation Survey

Executive summary

Altogether, 462 (as compared to 646 in 2023) responses were received (9% of current EAA Members).

- While 91% of the respondents attended the Annual Meeting (onsite, online or both), the non-attendance was mostly due to lack of time or timing incompatibility.
- Funding Annual Meeting attendance is an issue and not all participants can diversify the coverage of their costs.
- Most respondents thought the academic programme was of good quality and appreciated the diversity of topics, but found the number of parallel sessions too high and the session topics often similar and overlapping. A solution to the high number of parallel sessions and the overlaps might be to
 - extend the academic programme over another day;
 - refine abstract management software priorities in creating the academic programme so that it gives high priority not to overlap session tags;
 - increase quality control.
- Discussion should be enhanced.
- The limit of one oral and one poster contribution per person as main author suits most respondents.
- The concept of poster presentations should be reconsidered to allow more interaction with poster authors and increase the visibility of posters.
- The onsite organisation suffered from technical difficulties, deficient infrastructure, insufficient signage and lack of organisation. Many respondents found the catering very poor.
- The issues in online organisation derived from technical shortcomings and inappropriate local infrastructure; despite volunteers' and IT assistance, livestreaming problems impacted on the time schedule of sessions.
- While 51% of respondents did not attend any online sessions, 57% of respondents found the hybrid format useful. Majority of delegates (72%) support continuing the EAA Annual Meetings in hybrid format, whereas 23% would prefer to only hold them onsite. The All in the Loop statistics show a total of 6228 livestream views, an average of 17 remote participants per regular session, and 173 remote keynote sessions viewers (average of 29 remote participants per keynote session).
- As per the All in the Loop provider, 3798 delegates (73%) used the mobile app or the web version. Respondents provided feedback which will be shared with the provider.
- Majority of delegates (70%) attended the Fair onsite.
- Respondents reported no serious safety issues, but pointed out the impact of hot weather.
- Respondents would welcome
 - more emphasis on sustainability;
 - childcare possibilities;

- availability of multiple quiet rooms;
- possibilities to connect with fellow participants;
- larger spectrum of side events (e.g. organised by EAA Communities).
- The percentage of respondents planning to attend the 31st Annual Meeting in Belgrade onsite decreased from 67% in last year’s survey to 41% this year. The ratio of those deciding later increased from 23% last year to 42% this year, and the number of respondents not willing to attend rose from 3% to 10%.
- Most respondents (81%) agree that the printed Programme Book is no longer available in print.
- Since print copies will not be produced at all from 2025, the majority of respondents (66%) will read the *EJA* online via EAA website

Introduction

The evaluation survey of the 30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome (AM; 28 - 31 August 2024) and selected membership matters took place between 13 - 20 September 2024. Altogether 462 EAA Members responded in the 2024 evaluation survey in full; further 88 respondents started the survey but dropped out before completing it, and other 70 individuals viewed the survey but did not answer any question. The average time spent completing the survey was 15 minutes.

What is your current career stage / work situation?

494 responses

BA Student	2	0,4%
MA Student	14	2,83%
PhD Researcher	109	22,06%
Postdoctoral Researcher	88	17,81%
Temporary Position as Principal Investigator	18	3,64%
Temporary employment in contract/commercial archaeology	1	0,2%
Temporary employment in the heritage sector	11	2,23%
Permanent academic employment	114	23,08%
Permanent employment in contract/commercial archaeology	18	3,64%
Permanent employment in the heritage sector	41	8,3%
Other permanent employment	13	2,63%
Freelancer	19	3,85%
Retired	31	6,28%
Unemployed	4	0,81%
Other	11	2,23%

What is the country where you work, study or reside (rather than your nationality)?

494 respondents

Did you attend the 30th EAA Annual Meeting in Rome?

491 responses

Why did you not attend the 30th EAA Annual Meeting?

47 responses

- Most of the respondents did not attend due to lack of time or timing incompatibility.
- 6 respondents could not pay the registration fees.

My 30th EAA Annual Meeting registration, attendance and travel costs were covered (tick all that apply):

498 responses

- The breakdown of the funding opportunities per career stage / work situation gives the following results, showing that undergraduate students, freelancers, retired and unemployed almost entirely rely on their personal budget, whereas the other categories manage to diversify the coverage of their costs:

Career stage / work situation	by my employer / contractor	from a grant (including the OMF grants)	from my personal budget	from other sources
BA Student			2	
MA Student			9	2
PhD Researcher	39	19	51	9
Postdoctoral Researcher	38	21	32	3
Temporary Position as Principal Investigator	9	6	6	2
Temporary employment in contract/commercial archaeology			1	
Temporary employment in the heritage sector	4		2	2
Permanent academic employment	50	26	31	6
Permanent employment in contract/commercial archaeology	7	2	8	1
Permanent employment in the heritage sector	19	5	15	
Other permanent employment	2	1	5	0
Freelancer	1		12	1

Retired	3		17	2
Unemployed			2	
Other	2		8	1

Please comment on the academic programme of the 30th Annual Meeting (character, design and format).

299 respondents

- Most respondents thought the academic programme was of good quality and appreciated the diversity of topics, but found the number of parallel sessions too high and the session topics often similar and overlapping. A solution to the high number of parallel sessions and the overlaps might be to
 - extend the academic programme over another day;
 - refine abstract management software priorities in creating the academic programme so that it gives high priority not to overlap session tags).
- Some respondents suggested to extend the length of oral presentations to 20 minutes, which however would be a step back to before the 2016 Vilnius AM (since when oral presentations were shortened from 20 to 15 minutes as a measure to keep the AM programme schedule manageable).
- Some respondents pointed out the low quality of some papers which should not have been accepted. To address this, the session organisers and the Scientific Committee might implement higher quality control (e.g. suggesting to convert oral presentations to posters) and enhance structure and focus in the academic programme.
- Discussion within sessions should be enhanced – some respondents pleaded for more / longer discussion slots, while others would prefer a short slot for questions after each contribution. While the latter is not practical and would increase the time needed for each session, the current rule of 1 discussion slot per 2-hours session block might be reconsidered.

- Respondents commented on the technical (software, computing and infrastructure) difficulties which impacted both the onsite and online attendees and caused significant delays to many sessions.
- The location of e-posters should be more central to increase their exposure. Discussion with / feedback to poster authors should be enhanced.
- Signage within and between the different buildings was deficient.
- Many respondents highly appreciated volunteers' assistance.

In order to facilitate creation of the academic programme, the active participation at the 30th Annual Meeting was limited to one oral and one poster contribution per person as main author. Has this rule affected you?

446 respondents

- Most respondents (77%) accept or can accommodate to the limit of one oral and one poster contribution per person as main author.

Please evaluate the poster presentations, which were displayed on e-poster boards onsite and available in the mobile app.

424 respondents

- A total of 42% of respondents were keen to view the posters on e-banners, the web or the mobile app.
- A quarter of respondents (26%) would have preferred traditional printed posters display.
- Respondents commented that
 - they had no time to browse posters during the Annual Meeting;
 - posters should be displayed in a more prominent location;
 - the ecological impact of e-poster boards (in terms of power and technology) might be heavier than the traditional printed posters.

Please rate the onsite organisation of the 30th EAA Annual Meeting.

379 responses

- Over half (54%) of respondents rated the onsite organisation of the 30th EAA Annual Meeting positively, 23% were neutral and 23% thought it was poor.

Please comment on the onsite organisation of the 30th Annual Meeting.

297 responses

Positive comments appreciated

- Friendly atmosphere at the Annual Meeting
- Volunteers' efforts

Negative comments referred to

- Technical (software and venue infrastructure) problems in sessions, lack of air-conditioning
- Crowded registration

- Opening Reception (long queues to enter and disrespectful behaviour towards delegates, deficient catering, poor lighting and general lack of organisation)
- Poor signage within venue (lack of signposting, double room numbering) incl. poor signage for disabled, inaccurate maps
- Poor catering (low quality and quantity of lunch boxes, coffee breaks, lack of queue management and production of lot of waste) – food trucks would have much improved the situation
- Lack of information (eating facilities) or information provided late (free access to museums)

Please rate the online organisation of the 30th EAA Annual Meeting (please leave unanswered if you only attended onsite).

203 responses

- Less than half (40%) of respondents rated the onsite organisation of the 30th EAA Annual Meeting positively, 30% were neutral and 30% thought it was poor.

Please comment on the online organisation of the 30th Annual Meeting (please leave unanswered if you only attended onsite).

139 responses

- While respondents appreciated the possibility to attend online and include those who could not travel to Rome, they suggested that the fee for the online participants should be lower than the fee for the onsite attendees.
- Problems with the online element included:
 - Streaming
 - Internet access
 - Sound – a roving microphone would help the online attendees to follow discussion
- As a result of the technical issues, some sessions were much disturbed.
- The online component needs better infrastructure and more time to prepare.
- Respondents appreciated the volunteers' assistance.

- A list of cancelled presentations and presentations given online could be published in advance of the Annual Meeting.
- Session organisers should be in contact with the presenters in their session in advance and ensure that online presenters can connect.

Which hybrid format elements of the 30th EAA Annual Meeting applied to you (please tick all that apply)?

680 responses

How many sessions did you attend online?

354 responses

- Altogether 44% of respondents attended one or more online sessions in which they were not presenting or organising. On the contrary, 51% of respondents did not attend any online sessions.

Did you find the hybrid format of the 30th EAA Annual Meeting useful?

314 responses

- Altogether 57% of respondents found the hybrid format useful, as compared to 17% who did not have an opinion and 26% who found the hybrid format not useful.

Which hybrid format element do you think needs improvement the most (scale from 0 - does not need to improve at all, through to 100 - needs to improve significantly)? If you do not wish to rate an element, please leave the option unanswered.

- The elements needing improvement are ordered from those needing most improvement to those needing less improvement (but still significant one):
 - Onsite equipment (web cams, microphone, loudspeakers, etc.) need improvement the most – 70.8 score
 - Onsite volunteers / IT support – 56.6 score
 - Software used (All in the Loop + Zoom) – 54.3 score

- Behaviour of onsite participants (talking to the microphone, not moving from the camera, organisation of the discussion) – 51.2 score
- Remote presenters' equipment (headset, internet connection parameters) – 50.1 score
- Online test rooms – 46.2 score

Please comment on the hybrid format elements needing improvement.

177 responses

- Onsite room equipment must be checked in advance, ideally including roving microphones.
- Online presenters must check their own equipment in advance and submit a pre-recorded version of their presentation to the session organiser.
- More time needs to be devoted to checking the onsite equipment before the scheduled session start.
- Session organisers and volunteers onsite need to pay more attention to the online participants (e.g., talking to and repeating questions from the onsite audience into the mic). Some onsite presenters, however, find this requirement insulting and distracting. Portable microphones attached to the presenters' clothing might be a solution.
- The minimum technical equipment suggested comprises of at least 1 microphone and 1 camera for the presenter and 1 microphone and 1 camera for the room (the auditorium).
- Some respondents suggested that online participants may only be able to follow sessions, not present remotely, while others thought the hybrid format should be abandoned altogether.

How satisfied were you with the software used (if you did not use it, please leave the option unanswered)?

- Respondents gave the All in the Loop software an average of 56 points out of 100.
- Respondents gave the mobile app an average of 65 points out of 100.

Please comment on the All in the Loop software and/or the mobile app, specifying the context of your attendance (session organiser, presenter, attendee; if you did not use it, please leave the option unanswered).

135 responses

- The app allowed for single presentations to be marked as favourite, but were only shown within whole sessions in My Agenda and My Favourites.
- It was difficult to search fellow participants in the programme – searching for a name in the Attendees / Presenters did not match the result with their presentation.
- The navigation from the session page through the "View on Map" button linked to the location of the room, but in order to find the building, one had to click back to the „Maps & Navigation“ and the campus map.
- The auto-scrolling to the current time of day was problematic. By late afternoon each day, this could take several seconds, during which time I wished to look at a saved session to check the room number or exact time of a presentation.

- The copy process to the google calendar was not effective.
- There was no possibility of seeing only the starred posters.
- It should be possible to open several tabs and leave them open.
- There is no way to write the session organisers and speakers from the scientific program – one must go through the directory of participants.
- The time of posting a message in the Discussion section is missing and creating confusion.

I attended the 30th EAA Annual Meeting European Archaeology Fair

403 responses

- Majority of delegates (70%) attended the Fair onsite while only 5% visited the online exhibitors' profiles.
- Altogether 28% of respondents did not attend the Fair at all.

Please tick the reason that brings, or would most likely bring you, to visit the online profile of the European Archaeology Fair exhibitors (tick all that apply):

446 responses

- The foremost reason to visit the online exhibitors' profiles would be discounts on books or services offered, connected with the possibility to interact with the exhibitors.
- Attractiveness of gaming elements are negligible.

I experienced safety issues while attending the 30th EAA Annual Meeting (onsite or online).

401 responses

While 87.8% of respondents did not experience any safety issues while attending the Annual Meeting, 11.5% of respondents reported having experienced safety issues. However, only three respondents commented on heat, transport and lost property issues.

Please comment on any aspect of the 30th EAA Annual Meeting not covered by the above.

108 responses

Respondents commented on:

- The need to improve the quality of presentations at EAA Annual Meetings.
- The social aspect of the Annual Meeting which they appreciated.
- The lateness of the information provided prior to the Annual Meeting.
- The hot weather with regard to the timing of the Annual Meeting and the unsatisfactory air-conditioning; the heat may be a health risk.
- The need for sustainability esp. with regard to catering and social events.
- The prints must not use grey font as it is difficult to read to the visually impaired.
- The worthwhileness of the hybrid format, considering the low number of remote presenters and remote participants in each session. However, the All in the Loop statistics show a total of 6228 livestream views, an average of 17 remote participants per regular session, and 173 remote keynote sessions viewers (average of 29 remote participants per keynote session).
- The organisation of excursions which was not well executed.

Do you support continuing the EAA Annual Meetings in hybrid format (both onsite and online)?

408 responses

- Majority of delegates (72%) support continuing the EAA Annual Meetings in hybrid format, whereas 23% would prefer to only hold them onsite.

- A more detailed analysis shows that of those respondents that attended the Annual Meeting onsite or combined both onsite and online attendance, 64% (250 respondents) support continuing the hybrid format, whereas of those who attended online only, the support for the hybrid format is 80% (43 respondents).

Is there any feature, currently not present at EAA Annual Meetings, that you would recommend implementing?

113 responses

Respondents would welcome

- Clearer thematic structure of sessions.
- More grants for students.
- Possibility to connect with other attendees willing to share hotel rooms/accommodations in advance of the conference.
- Quiet rooms where delegates could work / listen to sessions online / relax from the crowds.
- Childcare.
- Repetition of / alteration of the Archaeo-sexism exhibition.
- Facility to meet fellow participants (useful e.g. for early career participants or those with lower social abilities).
- Rethinking posters (poster session / exposure schedule (authors explaining their work at given time) in association with sessions).
- Social media group
- Larger spectrum of side events (e.g. organised by EAA Communities).
- Warning to vendors in the vicinity of the Annual Meeting venue so that Annual Meeting participants can use their services.
- Assurance that members have permanent access to the *EJA* online for years for which they have been members, even if they have ceased to be current members (as they would have access to printed copies of the journal already on their bookshelves).

The 31st EAA Annual Meeting will take place on 3 – 6 September 2025 in Belgrade, Serbia; the same EAA Annual Meeting registration fees will apply to both onsite and online attendees. I plan to:

460 responses

- It must be noted that the percentage of respondents planning to attend onsite decreased from 67% in last year's survey to 41% this year. The ratio of those deciding later increased from 23% last year to 42% this year, and the number of respondents not willing to attend rose from 3% to 10%.
- While only 12 respondent commented, the foremost reasons for a decision to attend online or postponing the decision are the increased cost of onsite attendance. However, respondents also mentioned political and safety concerns.

In order to make EAA Annual Meetings more environmentally friendly, the Executive Board suggests to no longer offer printed Programme Book (currently available in print for a fee); the printed Programme Summary will continue to be part of the delegate's bag for free and the pdf Abstract Book will continue to be available for download for free as well.

451 responses

- Most respondents (81%) agree that the printed Programme Book is no longer available in print. A 15% of respondents would prefer to continue to have the possibility to order printed Programme Book (this does not corresponds to the number of Programme Books actually ordered this year: 178 – 3% - out of 5192 delegates).
- Altogether 18 respondents commented, pointing out e.g. the usefulness of the printed programme to visually impaired delegates or those who wish to return to it for reference later. If the EAA only prints the Programme Summary, it should be made slimmer and support ease of reading (black instead of grey print).

The print copy of the *European Journal of Archaeology (EJA)* has been available to EAA Members for a fee since 2022; as part of transferring to full Open Access, print copies will not be produced at all from 2025.

450 responses

- The majority of respondents (66%) will read the *EJA* online via EAA website, other 24% will read it through their institutional access, and 10% will not read the *EJA*.

Chat with EAA Official over TEA

Ariane Ballmer

Nationality: Swiss

Institution: Independent researcher

Position in the EAA: Vice President

EAA Member since: 2010

Photo at left courtesy of A. Ballmer

TEA: Was archaeology always your dream job? Why did you end up choosing archaeology in the end?

Ballmer: Archaeology was never really on my radar. In school, we were hardly taught anything about it. The TV documentaries I watched when I was young were terribly boring, and the museum exhibits I visited smelled awful. After qualifying for university entrance in 2000, when I was supposed to choose my field of study, I was generally enthusiastic about all sorts of directions— from primatology to music and from journalism to forestry. I spontaneously chose archaeology. I remember taking this decision within a few minutes. It seems as if I was somehow drawn to the subject matter I had hitherto no real connection to and to which I did not know what to expect of at all. I was instantly hooked and quickly discovered my passion for archaeology after starting my studies. I have never once regretted my choice. At the same time, I am still deeply interested in topics and discussions from other disciplines.

Photo at right: At Banteay Srei, a Hindu temple ruin in the Angkor area (Siem Reap, Cambodia) (August 2024). The temple complex, dating from the 10th century AD, alongside the numerous other temples of the Angkor site, is a key pillar of Cambodian identity. As a graduate student, I had the opportunity to work at Banteay Srei as an archaeologist for several months in the framework of a restoration project by the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC). Since then, I keep returning to Angkor regularly. Angkor will never stop to amaze me. Photo courtesy of A. Ballmer.

TEA: Some people say that culture (broadly speaking) is a luxury. Do you agree or disagree? Why?

Ballmer: Capacity for culture is intrinsic to humans.

Therefore, I do not think that having culture is a luxury. Our being is so saturated with culture that we

cannot separate it from ourselves. That being said, the recognition or awareness of culture, access to culture, engagement with culture, and the free expression of culture must (unfortunately) be considered privileges. It is no coincidence that every person's right to participate in social and cultural life is recognized as a human right.

TEA: If you could see only the future or only the past, which would you choose, and why?

Ballmer: Always the past. A certain degree of uncertainty and unpredictability constitutes the magic of life, doesn't it?

TEA: What/How does archaeology contribute to society at large?

Ballmer: Archaeology reveals and preserves the past and provides us with a temporal context backward in time, based on scientific criteria in a systematic and comprehensible manner. This context serves people and society as a reference for individual and collective self-perception, and may hence, in the best case, give meaning to the present. Radically speaking, one could say that nothing today makes sense without a relation to yesterday. At the same time, this context is never absolute. Something as grand as the past it also prone to abuse. An essential contribution our discipline can make against the instrumentalization of the past to political ends is the *active and open care* for the dynamic quality and diversity of past scenarios. We do this by constantly questioning, challenging, revising and complementing them. It is through consistent and unwavering communication of our findings, but also of the principles of science and the spirit of scientific debate to the general public that we can have a significant impact on how the past is being referred to.

TEA: If you could go back in time, would you go? Where and when?

Ballmer: No, I do not see any interest or excitement for myself in going back in time. I would be interested in spending a day as an animal, though. A deer, a wolf, an owl... actually, any wild animal!

TEA: Any advice to new archaeologists just starting out?

Ballmer: The same advice I would give to all aspiring or new professionals: Learn how to do good work. Find your own style. Be persistent. Beware of trolls.

Photo at left: At the Mozu tombs in Sakai (Osaka, Japan) (December 2024). A colleague from the University of Osaka I met at a conference 10 years ago, when working on ritual landscapes, led me to this fascinating ensemble of burial mounds featuring a unique keyhole shape, dating between the 3rd and the 6th century AD. Photo courtesy of A. Ballmer.

Meet a Member over TEA

Anne Leschallier de Lisle

Nationality: French

Institution: ARCHAÏOS

EAA Member since: 2024

Photo courtesy of A. Leschallier

TEA: How did you get into archaeology?

Leschallier de Lisle: I am a geographer specializing in geomatics, data management and agile IT project management, who is currently working as a Product Owner, responsible for designing, prioritising and managing a product's backlog (usually an application) to ensure it meets user needs while aligning development with business objectives. My initial career path seemed destined for urban planning rather than archaeology. However, as a discipline, geography tends to thrive on intersections with other fields; without a subject of study, it feels hollow. With over 80% of data being geolocated, the rise of technology and the democratization of cartography have enabled me to explore a variety of disciplines, each more fascinating than the last.

My journey into archaeology began with a job posting for the position of Scientific Manager of the Data Unit for the Al Ula Cultural Oasis Project (UCOP), funded and steered by Afalula¹ on behalf of the RCU² in Saudi Arabia, and carried out by Archaios, the organization by which I am now employed. The opportunity intrigued me, though I initially approached it with many preconceived notions. I enjoy challenging assumptions by confronting them with reality, immersing myself in new disciplines, and learning from their unique research methods, operational practices, and professional cultures. Archaeology did not disappoint!

This field has reignited a sense of curiosity and introduced me to perspectives and methodologies that differ significantly from those in geography. These experiences have enriched my understanding and allowed me to engage more deeply with interdisciplinary subjects rooted in spatiotemporal data, transforming these into meaningful spatial analyses. Archaeology has been a truly rewarding avenue for growth, discovery and intellectual exploration.

¹ French Agency for AIUla development

² Royal Commission for AIUla

TEA: What is the most important and relevant part of your work?

Leschallier de Lisle: My work revolves around two fundamental components: on one hand, the overall project data management, and secondly, research initiatives based on spatial data.

The first—data management—plays a critical role in ensuring the integrity, organization and accessibility of the data throughout the research process. Archaeological data, however, is incredibly ‘alive’—it is collected, analysed, excavated, reworked, interpreted and compared in an ongoing cycle. Coming from the world of IT and agile, where the concept of ‘done’ is an almost irrevocable outcome, adapting to this iterative and ever-evolving nature of archaeological data was a significant learning curve for me. The other aspect of data management that seems crucial to me is their relevance: What purpose do the data serve? What will they ultimately be used for?

While there is often a tendency to collect as much information as possible due to the time constraints of most projects, it is important to strike a balance between the time spent on data collection and update versus the real value this data adds to the project and the wider scientific community. This also touches on what I believe to be the most fundamental—and far too often overlooked—aspect of data management: the end-users of the data. Make data truly usable, necessitates the right tools, applications, devices and procedures. Striking a balance between how the data is designed, the tools chosen, and the profiles of the people working with it is key. And by "profiles," I don't only refer to job roles, but also to the personalities and working styles of the individuals involved.

It is often said that tools should be adapted to the user, but this view is somewhat idealistic. While it is indeed a priority to adapt tools to meet users' needs and available resources, I firmly believe that supporting change management is just as crucial. This includes building capacity within the team and adopting new tools that prioritize analysis over tedious tasks like data cleaning or repetitive data entry, for instance. That said, rest assured—I'm far from being a staunch advocate of an all-digital approach!

The second major component of our work involves applying spatial analyses to archaeology. Over the years, we have developed an archaeological map of our survey area with a high degree of accuracy, a process that combines meticulous vectorisation with the input of qualitative data into a comprehensive database. This foundation enables us to carry out some truly exciting spatial analyses of the oasis.

Image at right shows data processing and creation of DEM (Digital Elevation Model), al-Ula office, UCOP 2023 field season. Photo by Salomé Sepeau © Archaïos.

One of our primary objectives is to reconstruct past landscapes to better understand the historical development of the oasis. This involves studying hydraulic systems, analyzing the morphology of streets and agricultural plots, and examining the composition of dwellings.

These analyses benefit from the collaboration and expertise of the project's diverse specialists whose insights are cross-referenced through the spatial nature of the data.

TEA: Describe your workspace in five words or less

Leschallier de Lisle: Noise-cancelling headphones, coffee, music, Post-its and... WhatsApp!

TEA: What is the one piece of gear that you can't live without in the field?

Leschallier de Lisle: My pillow! My yoga mattress! And—above all—coffee!

TEA: How does archaeology affect your daily life?

Leschallier de Lisle: Working in archaeology has profoundly changed the way I view my surroundings. There are two concrete examples of this change. Today, when I walk through my village, I now pay close attention to the materials used in construction, the orientation of the houses, and the position of entrances and windows (speaking of, why do so many face north?), and the organization of neighbourhoods and roads. I analyze old street layouts to account for the past organization of a settlement, even for relatively recent developments, and consider why changes occurred. Additionally, I find myself interpreting the field divisions around my home and the remains of some islands across the way. Finally, I've developed a habit of looking down while walking, always on the hunt for a pottery shard!

TEA: If you could see only the future or only the past, which would you choose, and why?

Leschallier de Lisle: It's such a difficult choice! The possibilities are intriguing: would it be a single time jump or several? Could I return, or would I be fully immersed?? Would I have control over the location(s)?

If I could go back in time, I would choose several moments, and not necessarily to be present in historical moments and places, but rather in different periods far removed from the same places, those to which we belong because we love them. I'd love to see my coastline in Neolithic times or in the 17th century and watch our ancestors' daily lives from the sidelines! I'd love to experience ordinary details: the inside of houses, the taste of water, and the rhythms of life. The past feels tangible, a chance to witness the foundations of what shaped us.

At the same time, the future is also fascinating. What do advancements in AI and changes in the international geopolitical context have in store for us? How will our professions evolve? I'll try to imagine scenarios and compare them with what I can observe in the future, to see if I've got it wrong, and somewhere down the line I'll be reassured to know that not everything is written in advance. Likewise, being aware of the future would undoubtedly enable me to be even more committed to the life choices I make.

TEA: Some people say that culture is a luxury. Do you agree or disagree? Why?

Leschallier de Lisle: I really don't agree with the idea that culture is a luxury. Culture, in the broadest sense, is everything that encompasses the shared traditions, beliefs and practices around which groups of human beings, and then entire societies, are organized. This seems to me to be fundamental, because it is almost the defining characteristic of humanity. Culture is alive and 'spongy'; it shapes our identity; it creates links between people. It's incredible and fascinating to see that, given equivalent environmental contexts, we can study societies that have developed differently, or *vice versa*. Different beliefs, different social organizations, different homes, different languages... Culture represents the impossibility of nothingness, curiosity about others and for others, whether in the present, the past, or distant places. Of course, some forms of culture, such as the fine arts or certain shows, can be considered as luxuries in specific contexts, but the essence of culture—stories, music, rituals, and heritage—is part of all human communities, whatever their social or economic status. And luxury remains a very relative concept!

Image above shows photogrammetry of an excavated canal in the Wadi Mutad'il Valley to the north-east of the al-Ula oasis, UCOP 2023 field season. Photo by Salomé Sepeau © Archaïos.

New Discovery

Another Illyrian helmet discovered at Gomile in Zakotorac on the peninsula of Pelješac, Croatia

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²*Dubrovnik Museums, Croatia*

³*Institute of Archaeology, Zagreb, Croatia*

Just a few months ago, an excavation team at the necropolis of Gomile discovered another Illyrian helmet which captured international media attention such as the Associated Press, Euronews, and *Archaeology Magazine*. It is one of rare places outside Greece and Macedonia where more than one helmet was discovered, which is indication that this extraordinary site has huge importance for understanding relations between Greeks and indigenous communities. Though a detailed publication is forthcoming (?), the following is an account of the find placed in context with ongoing (?) excavations at the site in relation to the larger archaeological landscape in which it was situated.

The Site of Zakotorac

The hamlet of Zakotorac belongs to the village of Donja Banda in the municipality of Orebić. It is located in the central part of the Pelješac peninsula on only road running from east to west across the peninsula. A prehistoric hillfort was probably located on nearby Kotorac hill (elevation 413.8), which still dominates the east-west road mentioned above. At the top of the hill is the church of St. Michael the Archangel, locally called the Church of the Guardian Angels. A large necropolis with at least 27 stone mounds is located about 200 m southwest from Kotorac hill at the site Gomile. See Figure 5. However, this necropolis is integral part of larger archaeological landscape.

Figure 5. Hillfort on Kotorac Hill and necropolis near village. Photo by Miroslav Vuković.

West of Kotorac hill is a line of stone mounds which lead to Vidohovo spring, followed by a larger mound group south of the hamlet of Golubinica. These mounds (ca 10) have more "classic" appearance; they present as plain heaps of stone either with or without a border. Some are considerably damaged by stone robbing. The use of the stones for more recent construction revealed some of the graves. The graves were made of stone slabs which appear to be made for inhumations placed in the contracted position. All of the above suggests a date from the very end of the Eneolithic to the Late Bronze Age. Obvious human intervention (monumental stone slabs in form of a wall) and its position in accordance with mounds make Vidohovo spring the pivotal point of the cultural landscape although it is very hard to judge its chronology and meaning.

Constructions

Of the at least 27 stone mounds (or similar drystone constructions) that have been identified on the site so far, two basic types can be singled out: flat mounds with outer stone rings and step-like mounds with two or three stone rings. Almost all mounds have several drystone constructions (probably tombs) added on the outer side of the stone rings by which they are surrounded. This kind of mound construction has known parallels at the sites of Nakovana on Pelješac as well as in necropolis at Kopila near Blato on Korčula. See Figure 6. These similarities in the mound construction already indicated that mounds on the site of Gomile in Zakotorac could also be dated in the Iron Age. Unlike similar necropolis in Nakovana, however, no flat graves have yet been found in Zakotorac. One unique feature of the Gomile site which finds no parallels elsewhere are the small drystone constructions added on the outer rim of mounds, next to large annexes with tombs containing multiple burials. While these do not seem to be graves, their purpose is still unknown.

Figure 6. Map of sites mentioned in the text. Map by Domagoj Perkić.

Graves

So far, fieldwork coordinated by the Croatian Centre for Prehistoric Research has excavated mounds 1 and 5 and their adjoining constructions. In mound 1 we discovered four graves and two large annexes/tombs added on the outer ring of the mound. Both of these annexes also had the above-mentioned small drystone constructions leaning on them. The graves within the mound had rather small numbers of finds as well as human remains compared to the abundance of finds discovered in two annexes. Both tombs contained more than ten deceased individuals and hundreds of different grave goods. (Perkić, Dizdar & Potrebica 2021)

Figure 7. Zakotorac—Mound 5. Image by Miroslav Vuković.

Mound 5 was obviously a central point for the necropolis. Between the 6th and 4th century BC, around ten burial chambers were built within an initial stone ring. See Figure 7. Most of these chambers contained more than one individual, and some even contained more than ten! The area to the east of the bordering ring was tightly filled with different annexes containing burial chambers with multiple burials and numerous grave goods which also dated to the period between the 4th and 3th century BC. See Figures 8-9. Several smaller drystone constructions were also discovered within and outside initial mound ring, probably for the placement of votive gifts (of which the most prominent was the helmet; see below). The central part of the mound was filled with stone and another two concentric stone

rings were inserted at that time in mound's fill. The construction ended with a central tomb dating to the 4th or 3rd century BC which was probably robbed. This is also the date of the graves added outside of the perimeter wall of mound 5.

Figure 8. Detail of grave goods from Zakotorac Mound 5. Photo by Domagoj Perkić.

Figure 9. Excavation of a grave at Zakotorac. Included in image is excavator Borut Križ. Photo by Domagoj Perkić.

Archaeological Finds

While some of the graves contained only several finds, some of the grave chambers contained hundreds of grave goods obviously belonging to several people. Finds belonged both to male and female individuals and included a wide range of objects and materials from Greece, local pottery vessels, body ornaments and weapons made of silver, bronze and/or iron and even glass and amber beads.

Pottery

While pottery was very scarce in some graves, others were much richer in such finds (e.g., at least 31 different vessels of Greek origin in grave 1 near mound 1) which is obviously connected with the graves' chronologies. The majority of Greek pottery could be dated to the 4th century BC, although there were both older as well as younger pieces (e.g. *Gnathia* types). Interestingly, Greek pottery at the site seems to have come from three major source areas: mainland Greece, southern Italy and Sicily (Magna Grecia) and the northern Italian Adriatic coast. So, it seems that the prehistoric community at the site was well connected, as they were involved with at least three different Greek trade networks. However, evidence for deliberate fragmentation and the special position of pottery fragments in the grave indicates that these objects must have been very valuable to their indigenous owners. At Gomile, Greek pottery was used in specific local burial rituals which were completely different from contemporary Greek context for similar finds. It is also interesting that the local pottery (which is hard to discern both typologically and chronologically) appears to a much lesser extent and then only in the stone filling of the mounds.

Metal finds

Metal finds suggest that both male and female individuals were buried in the same chambers; this conclusion has also been confirmed by anthropological analysis of the bones. Metal finds fall in two major categories: weapons and body ornaments. The body ornaments are mainly made of bronze with a few exceptions (of silver fibulae). Some pieces were functional in relation to clothing (e.g. fibulas and pins). Both fibulae and pins appear in the largest numbers as far as body ornaments go; they are also the best indicators of chronology. The overall distribution of individual types of fibulae and pins at the same time outlines the extent of communication networks (Perkić, Dizdar & Potrebica 2024). However, graves at Zakotorac also contained large number of other bronze ornaments such as diadems, hair ornaments, necklaces, bracelets, rings, belts, *saltaleoni*, tweezers and pendants. These other ornament categories offer mute witness to wealth and power of the people who lived there.

Weapons were usually made of iron and are badly preserved. They mostly include different kinds of spears, though there are fragments of curved single-edged swords as well as one well-preserved *xiphos*. All of this suggests a well-armed and powerful local warrior elite.

Figure 10. Helmet found at Zakotorac Mound 5 *in situ*. Photo by Domagoj Perkić.

Figure 11. Helmet found at Zakotorac Mound 1 after restoration. Photo by Miroslav Vuković.

Helmets

The only armaments made of bronze (which are also the most exquisite finds from the necropolis) are two Graeco-Illyrian helmets. The first helmet was discovered in 2020 in grave 1 near mound 1. It was placed in small compartment surrounded by a drystone wall leaning in a vertical position against the stone wall which separated it from grave 1 (large chamber built on the outside of the stone ring encircling the mound). The space beside the helmet contained only several fragments of Greek pottery. The second helmet was discovered in 2024 (also in separate space within the inner circle of mound 5, but outside of any particular grave) surrounded with stone and placed in a vertical position. See Figure 10-11. The fact that both helmets were found outside specific graves, in secluded and obviously separate space, and in vertical position suggest that they are not part of any specific grave inventory but act as votive gifts related to the specific burial chamber or even to the mound itself. They all belong to the same type (III A2-a) which could be dated from the end of 6th to the beginning of the 4th century BC.

Amber and glass

Characteristic of 5th-4th c BC graves in this region is an abundance of amber and glass beads. For example, grave 1 in mound 1 contained more than 500 different amber and glass beads that probably belonged to necklaces and/or bracelets.

Anthropology and Dating

As mentioned, most of the burial chambers contained several individuals. Since the remains were heavily mixed (there is almost no anatomical placement), we will determine MNIs for each chamber by the most numerous skeletal remains (teeth, in most cases for the recent excavation finds). Preliminary bioarchaeological analysis shows that grave 1 contained at least 13 individuals: 10 adults and three children. However, the radiocarbon (14C) analysis of two samples (also teeth) from two different individuals suggest that people buried in these graves come from at least two periods: one at the end of the Late Bronze Age (980–810 BC) and another at the beginning of the Late Iron Age (380–170 BC). On the other hand, the grave goods and costume items belong exclusively to the 4th century BC, which means that individual(s) from the 10th–9th century BC were placed in these graves without any (visible) grave goods. While bioarchaeological analysis for the majority of the bone material is still underway, it is worth noting that the same situation has been observed in several other cases. Some of the deceased show signs of *perimortem* trauma probably related to violence.

Further Research

While these data offer up new insights about the funerary customs of the prehistoric communities in the area, they also open up numerous new questions. The radiocarbon dating and anthropological analysis that are forthcoming will give the exact number of the deceased and their age. If funds are provided, genetic research will also be carried out in order to determine whether any biological relationship existed between the individuals within this population and strontium and other isotope analysis may shed some light on their mobility and diet patterns.

Conclusion

This is an exceptionally valuable site on numerous levels. Gomile's unique funerary architecture (again, the closest parallels are at Nakovana—also Pelješac—and at Kopila on the nearby island of Korčula) suggest that a special cultural area developed in the southern part of the eastern Adriatic coast between the 6th and the 1st century BC. The abundance and diversity of grave goods indicate not only the wealth but also the powerful socioeconomic position of this community in relation to several communication networks. Some of these networks obviously included Greek trade, but others went much further along the Adriatic coast as well as deep into what we could now call the Balkan inlands. In any case, study of this site and community will significantly change our understanding of indigenous Iron Age communities and their obviously much more active role in the process of the Greek colonisation of the Adriatic and further relations with local communities.

Team

The research in Zakotorac is coordinated by the Centre for Prehistoric Research whose president is Prof. Hrvoje Potrebica. The core research team consists of Prof. Hrvoje Potrebica, Ph.D. (the University of Zagreb, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Department of Archaeology), Domagoj Perkić, Ph.D., director of the Archaeological Museum of the Dubrovnik Museums and Marko Dizdar, Ph.D., director of the Institute of Archaeology in Zagreb. Beside several other collaborators from core institutions, thus far, several other researchers and institutions collaborated in this project: Borut Križ, Ph.D. (Dolenjski Museum in Novo mesto, Slovenia), Marta Kalebota (the Municipal Museum of Korčula), Miona Miliša, Ph.D. dean of the Academy of Arts in Split (conservation and restoration). This year also beside students from the University of Zagreb, the fieldwork included students from the University of Salento (Lecce) as a pilot for international cooperation between Croatian and Italian universities. See Figure 12.

Figure 12. The Zakotorac team. Image collage by Domagoj Perkić.

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Research Overview

Neanderthals made the first complex structure for tar extraction in Vanguard Cave (Gibraltar)

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A scientific study published in the journal *Quaternary Science Reviews* (Ochando et al., 2024), described, for the first time, a structure used by Neanderthals 60,000 years ago in Gibraltar. This structure – a pit dug into the ground at Vanguard Cave – would have been used to extract plant resins. The findings of this study are highly significant because they reveal complex levels of cognition in Neanderthals. Our study suggests that the Neanderthals who utilized the site understood the plants that they needed to select and the complex industrial process required for the manufacture of tar.

Neanderthals utilized tar obtained from woody plants as an adhesive for the hafting of stone points onto wooden shafts and making spears for use in the ambush hunting of prey (Koller et al., 2001; Maza et al., 2006; Pawlik and Thissen, 2011; Degano et al., 2019; Niekus et al., 2019; Schmidt et al., 2024). Until now, how they actually obtained the tar necessary for hafting was unknown. Previous theoretical studies have proposed two methods by which tar could have been made. Though simple, one of these methods produced markedly low yields: it involved the open air combustion of birch bark. A second (more complex) method would have required the anoxic heating of fragments of woody plants, such as birch. This second method required fragments of woody plants to have been buried and heated with fire in isolation from oxygen, so that they would exude resin without the wood catching fire. Which of these two methods was actually used has great implications regarding Neanderthals' cognitive capacities, as the more complex method required a higher level of organization and technical know-how.

Vanguard Cave (VC) is located at sea level on the promontory of Gibraltar at the south of the Iberian Peninsula. See Figure 13. Gibraltar is situated on the northern coast of the Strait of Gibraltar, which connects the Mediterranean Sea with the Atlantic Ocean.

Figure 13. Location of Vanguard Cave in Southern Iberian Peninsula.

The Neanderthals' hunting ground in this area was located on the now-submerged coastal shelf off the eastern side of Gibraltar and stretched for up to 4.5 kilometres from the caves. It has been

previously described as a “Mediterranean Serengeti”, consisting of a system of sand dunes with scattered stone pine woodland and copses of Mediterranean vegetation and seasonal lakes. The area attracted a diverse animal groups, including red deer, ibex, wild horse, aurochs and wild boar, among others. The local Neanderthals would have hafted their carefully-crafted stone points (of typical Mousterian type in flint and quartzite) onto wooden shafts, using the tar they had produced to create lethal weapons that could be used to hunt a variety of animals. They may have also used such spears to defend against the many dangerous predators that roamed this ancient landscape, including Pleistocene lions, leopards, spotted hyaenas, wolves and brown bears.

The hearth structure of interest was discovered during excavations in Vanguard Cave in the year 2019. See Figure 14. This cave is part of the Gorham’s Cave Complex, which was inducted as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 2016 as part of the United Kingdom’s list of sites. Once again, Vanguard Cave has shown that its peculiar environmental conditions – the rapid advance of a sand dune which sealed off the material evidence – have allowed the unique conservation of Neanderthal activities.

Figure 14. Plan of Vanguard Cave site and pictures showing the section profiles and pit section.

Structure reconstruction

The results of the 2024 study (Ochando et al., 2024) support previous theoretical predictions regarding the use of the second more complex anoxic heating method for tar production (Koller et al., 2001; Kozowyk et al., 2017; Schmidt et al., 2023). The structure that was discovered in Vanguard Cave resembles a simple hollow in the cave sediment. This simplicity may explain why such structures may not have been recognised in the past. It is only now, after a wide range of analyses involving the collaboration of an interdisciplinary team, that it has been possible to show that the pit was used as a chamber for anoxic heating.

We propose the following sequence of events (See Figure 15) for the preparation of the structure:

- T-0 and T-1: Layer 10 excavation of a central circular area with two outlet channels reinforced by compacted sand. Bends at layer 9c were made by hand or through the use of a flat wooden tool by someone facing the entrance. The placement of carbonate rocks in the channels or the structure (as can be observed in Figure 15) likely to have stabilised the cover.
- T-2: Rockrose leaves were placed in the pit, then heated. Thereafter, the trough would be sealed, thus preventing oxidation.
- T-3: A layer of guano was added to the underlying sand to give consistency to the structure and perhaps improve thermal/oxygen insulation.
- T-4: A fire was laid over the trough, which affected the contents of the pit as well as the guano layer.
- T-5: After combustion, the colour and texture of the guano would have been altered and could have originated the hard crust with the white spherules.
- T-6: Excavation and recovery of the material placed in the pit (rockrose resin). This altered guano crust appears to have been broken in order to access material deposited in the pit.
- T-7: Infilling of the pit by charcoal-enriched sediments and sealing of the structure by layer 9f.
- T-8: Pitch hot

Figure 15. The anthropogenic structure could have been made following these steps. From T-0 to T-8.

It was truly fortunate that the rapid advance of the sand dune c. 60,000 years ago facilitated the 'sealing' of the described structure (Pettitt and Bailey, 2000; Jiménez-Espejo et al., 2013; Rodríguez-Vidal et al., 2013; Doerschner et al., 2019). As a result, there was excellent preservation of pollen grains and spores, which have allowed confirmation of the ecological conditions outside the cave (Carrión et al., 2008, 2018).

Structure function

Palynological, anthracological, anthropological and organic geochemical analyses suggest that the fuel used in the structure seems to have been grass (*Poaceae*) and other herbaceous vegetation, as well as shrub taxa (*Cupressaceae* and *Erica*). Compared to burning solely hard woods, which yield embers with a higher calorific value, the grass fire enabled both lower, more regulated temperatures and faster combustion. Fragments of *Cistaceae* charcoal found in a pyrophytic context support the idea that the plant material was burned under controlled conditions within the pit.

Different methods were used to confirm the function of the structure. These included an archaeological experiment which showed that the pit, including its dimensions, were compatible with the extraction of tar. See Figure 16. It seems, from the results obtained, that the tar was extracted from gum rockrose (*Cistus ladanifer*) instead of birch. Birch would have been a rare tree in these Mediterranean latitudes, whereas rockroses would have been abundant. It is worth noting that the labdanum (or resin) obtained from rockrose has been used in perfumes, as a cough treatment, and even as an antiseptic until the 20th century (Morgado et al., 2005; Martín et al., 2009; Frazão et al., 2018).

Figure 16. Experiment 4: The pit structure was built by hand according to the morphology and dimensions defined by the archaeological excavations in Vanguard Cave (Layers 9 and 10).

Conclusions

From these new analyses we can conclude that Neanderthals were able to build intricate, multi-layered hearths with particular technological goals in mind. Those goals may have included the development of tools, medicines, and/or weapons. For the first time, we discovered a Neanderthal's specialized burning structure compatible with essential oil steam distillation from rockroses

(*Cistaceae*) for tar manufacture at the Vanguard Cave in layers that are geochronologically well constrained. We tested our interpretations empirically by constructing a structure that resembled the one unearthed at VC in terms of composition and morphology. By distilling a tiny bunch of young rockrose leaves in a confined, nearly anoxic environment for a fair amount of time, a quantity of tar more than sufficient to haft two spearheads could be produced using only the equipment and supplies that were accessible in the area during the period in question.

This study may serve as a starting point and a reference for other researchers when identifying similar structures in other archaeological sites. However, only through interdisciplinary work was it possible to achieve such a realistic reconstruction of the original structure.

The research was undertaken under the direction of the Gibraltar National Museum, who are responsible for the maintenance of the World Heritage Site, in collaboration with the University of Murcia and the Instituto Andaluz de Ciencias de la Tierra (CSIC). In all, the study briefly described here (see Ochando et al., 2024) required the participation of a group of 31 scientists from five countries and involved over 15 different disciplines, including palaeobotany, archaeology, ichnology, geochemistry, mineralogy and ecology in order to show that the tar extraction structure at VC could only have been made purposely by Neanderthals some 60,000 years ago.

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Debate

Should archaeology simply cancel plastics?

Yvonne Shashoua

National Museum of Denmark

Malignant! Wicked! Toxic! These terms might bring to mind descriptions of some world leaders or conflict situations, but in actuality they have all been recently used to describe plastics in our material heritage and archaeological sites (Scott 2002 and British Archaeology 2024). While I might use the slang ‘wicked’ to describe the plastic spacesuit worn by Andreas Mogensen, the first Danish astronaut in 2015, I cannot imagine that professional bodies like ICOM and EAA applaud the application of such negatively biased terminology to the materials in our care. In our modern world, where the policies and practices of inclusivity are promoted, I question why plastics are being cancelled in archaeology publications and how it affects their perceived value as artefacts as well as for use in both conservation and as storage materials.

First, I will introduce plastics and why they degrade from a scientific perspective. Next, I follow with three cases of heritage materials to illustrate why archaeology should not cancel plastics. I contend that plastics are both a substantial part of our material heritage in modern times and an important tool in contemporary archaeological work.

Plastics 101

Plastics comprise macromolecules or polymers (more than 99% by weight) that are modified with additives (antioxidants, thermal stabilizers) and shaped to convert them from liquids to solids. Polymerisation reactions, the selection of additives and fillers, and shaping technique all contribute to the physical and chemical properties of plastics, and to their degradation pathways and lifetimes.

The polymer component in the first manmade plastics (developed between 1850 and 1910), originated from natural sources such as cellulose from trees and casein protein from milk. Natural polymers were chemically treated with acids (cellulose acetate and nitrate) or formaldehyde (casein-formaldehyde) to modify their chemical properties and produce physically stable, mouldable products. However, since the 1950s, almost all plastics have been synthetic, and their polymer components formed by chemically bonding together thousands of small gas molecules such as ethylene, propylene and styrene (monomers) rather than chemically treating natural polymers. Because of their low cost, 96% of monomers are derived from crude oil, natural gas or coal, all of which are non-renewable or fossil sources (Plastics Europe 2021). Although it is possible to synthesize chemically identical polymers from renewable resources such as waste biomass, less than 5% of plastics produced today are bio-based. This discrepancy is largely due to cost.

The degradation of plastics may be envisioned as a reversal of their chemical syntheses. When plastics are exposed to oxygen in air, heat, light or mechanical forces, the additives that protect polymers work until they are exhausted. As exposure continues, the chemical bonds comprising the side chains and backbone of the polymer break sequentially from the weakest to the strongest. Light, particularly ultraviolet (UV) light with wavelengths 200 - 800nm, is the most damaging factor leading to the degradation of plastics. Because bond energies in polymers are typically between 300 and 500kJ per mole, they can withstand visible and infrared light with energies 300 and 180kJ per mol respectively. By contrast, UV light contains sufficient energy to break the strongest chemical bonds in polymers (McNeill 1992). This results in physical disintegration of plastics.

In heritage collections, significant symptoms of plastic degradation include yellowing, stickiness, shrinkage, brittleness and flaking. Together, these result in loss of function, form and/or interpretation. In natural environments (including archaeological sites), the most frequently recorded symptom of plastics' degradation is their fragmentation into particles or fibers known as microplastics (<5 mm) (Zhang et al. 2021). Identified for the first time in 2004, microplastics are the largest particles that can be inhaled or ingested and subsequently transported into the living tissues of animals, fish, birds, insects, and humans (Thompson et al. 2004). Microplastics are not the final stage of the degradation process. In fact, they merely represent the last stage detectable by the naked eye. Smaller nanoplastics (0.05-5mm) have been detected in air, water, and food (Chen et al. 2021) and the complete degradation of plastics to carbon dioxide in soil is known as mineralization (Huo et al. 2024).

The first carbon-neutral, bio-based plastic dates from 1862

Although bio-based plastics are thought of as novel materials, the very first plant-based plastics date from 1862 when they were made by reacting natural cellulose derived from cotton and fibres or wood pulp with concentrated acids (Stannett 1951). One advantage of this from an environmental perspective is that plants store atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) during growth. Therefore, using bio-based sources to produce plastics removes CO₂ from the atmosphere and fixes it throughout a product's lifetime (Weiss et al. 2012).

Causing cellulose to react with acids (known as acetylation), transforms the insoluble, non-formable, cellulose polymer into readily soluble, transparent cellulose acetate plastic that can be cast into sheets and spun into textile fibers. In the early 20th century, cellulose acetate replaced rare and expensive natural materials such as ivory, tortoiseshell, and mother of pearl in high value, functional products such as hair combs, spectacle frames and cutlery handles (Meade et al. 1905). It was also substituted for inflexible, heavy glass in photographs and tracing sheets.

Because acetic acid is the major product of deacetylation, and the degradation of artefacts and photographic film gives off a vinegar-like odour, the process is also known as 'vinegar syndrome'. Importantly, acetic acid vapour also catalyses degradation of other organic materials, including paper, and it corrodes metals. See Figure 17. If unchecked, 5-20 years after the initial symptoms of deacetylation are visible, cellulose acetate is reduced back to natural cellulose. In contrast to synthetic polymers based on fossil sources (that degrade to microplastics), cellulose acetate forms paper fibres that are considered harmless to human and animal health. See Figure 18.

Figure 17. Acetic acid produced by degrading knife handles from the 1950s has attacked the tissue in which they have been wrapped. The knife blades have been corroded by acetic acid.

Figure 18. Acid detection strips enclosed with the spoons indicate that the spoon handle in good condition (left side of image) gives off acetic acid, while the highly deteriorated example (right side of image) produces none. The handle on the right has degraded to cellulose.

No plastics - no space suits

Although its first application was as an effective replacement for rubber in electrical cable insulation during World War II, today plasticized polyvinyl chloride (PVC) is the second most highly consumed plastics material in the world. This is mainly due to its high flexibility (think of, e.g. garden hoses), its excellent ability to serve as a barrier to air and water (e.g. blood and colostomy bags, inflatable furniture, shower curtains), high flame retardancy (e.g. electrical insulation cables) and ability to mimic natural materials such as human skin (e.g. Barbie dolls).

PVC polymerization involves chemically adding thousands of vinyl chloride gas molecules together to produce a rigid solid material with a high molecular weight. Plasticizers or softeners are essential to increase the workability, flexibility and elongation of PVC and act by lubricating each polymer chain. Plasticization may be visualized as tossing cooked spaghetti (polymers) in olive oil to prevent the individual noodles sticking together. The more plasticizer, the more flexible the resulting PVC plastic. For example, electrical cables contain up to 30% plasticizer by weight, while fishing waders contain up to 50%. Phthalates – the chemicals used to soften, strengthen and improve the flexibility of plastics – have been widely used as plasticizers since the 1950s. However, after their identification as endocrine disruptors, their use today is frequently restricted and they are often substituted with alternatives.

Spacesuits developed for the Apollo program (1962-1972) were groundbreaking in their design, materials and construction. Although more than 50 years have passed since completion of the final Apollo mission, the spacesuits worn by Andreas Mogensen retain many of the original design features. See Figure 19. For example, the spacesuits and liquid cooling undergarments comprise at least ten different plastic types that protect the wearer and allow them to breathe, move unhindered, maintain a comfortable body temperature and carry out extra-vehicular activities using a Portable Life Support System. Liquid cooling undergarments comprise a tight-fitting fabric with a network of thin plasticized PVC tubing sewn onto the fabric. Circulating water in the tubing transports heat away from the astronaut's skin. The Portable Life Support System is a backpack that connects to the space suit via plasticized PVC hoses. They transport breathable oxygen to the wearer.

Figure 19. Spacesuit worn by Andreas Mogensen during a flight to the International Space Station in 2015, now in the collections of the National Museum of Denmark. The PVC hoses connecting to the Portable Life Support System can be seen supported by the right glove and crossing the body of the suit.

A 2000 study of the earlier spacesuits from the Apollo program undertaken by the National Air and Space Museum in Washington DC revealed that the plasticized PVC tubing in the liquid cooling undergarments as well as the hoses in the Portable Life Support System were stiff, had already changed colour (from transparent to dark brown), were tacky to the touch and their surfaces were obscured by white crystals. See Figure 20. Analyses suggested that the discolouration was due to oxidation of PVC polymer, the tackiness was caused by migration of phthalate plasticizer to surfaces and a subsequent chemical reaction with water produced white, phthalic acid crystals (Shashoua et al. 2002). To proactively combat such degradation, a preventive conservation strategy has been developed by the National Museum of Denmark to prolong the lifetime of plasticized PVC in Andreas Mogensen's suit beyond the 30 years achieved by the Apollo Space program's materials

Figure 20. PVC tubing from the Apollo spacesuits became stiff, discoloured and developed white crystals at surfaces after 30 years in storage.

Conservation and archaeology *need* plastics!

Low density polyethylene (LDPE) was synthesized from ethylene gas by chance in 1933 and was used to insulate radar sets at the outbreak of World War II. Today it is the most produced polymer globally. Its success as a polymer is due to its long, branched chain structure that imparts high flexibility without the need for plasticizers. LDPE can withstand temperatures ranging from -50°C to 85°C . Because LDPE is highly resistant to water, water vapour, acids and bases but permeable to oxygen and carbon dioxide, it is used for bags, packaging films, geomembranes and containers for transporting and storing food and chemicals.

LDPE's optical, thermal and chemical properties make it suitable for labelling, protecting, storing and treating archaeological artefacts and site samples including soils, geological materials and water. Resealable or ziplock bags have been commercially available since 1973 and evolved from the Danish

inventor Borge Madsen's "separable fastener" design, that replaced zipper teeth with interlocking plastic tracks (Macneal 2015). Unlike the paper envelopes and glass containers previously used to package artefacts and samples, enclosing artefacts and samples in resealable LDPE bags prior to storage in a refrigerator or freezer (at 4°C and -20°C, respectively) allows immediate access to the artefacts while also providing protection from condensation when removed from the cold. See Figure 21.

Figure 21. Museum objects and archaeological samples stored in a fridge are both accessible and protected by enclosing them in polyethylene bags.

Polyethylene sheets, bags and food containers are also used in terrestrial and marine environments to store samples and to preserve sites and remains or as part of *in situ* conservation. Much of the data informing on the time and pathways taken for plastics to degrade in natural environments are based on modelling studies, where samples are exposed to high intensities of light for short periods, and the changes that occur in their properties are recorded. From this, the data are extrapolated out to model the effects at the scale of years (Chamas et al. 2020). However, there can be a great deal of variability in the resulting models. For example, reported degradation times for plastic bags range from 10–1000 years.

A recent study of the degradation of plastics including polyethylene bags and containers in real time in coastal weather and marine environments over a three-year period suggested that LDPE degraded significantly faster when exposed to air, sunlight and precipitation than underwater or in sediments where the concentration of light and oxygen is lower (Shashoua et al. 2024). See Figure 22. In addition, black bags and containers showed greater resistance to oxidation than white and transparent examples.

Figure 22. In a recent study by the National Museum of Denmark, plastic bags and containers were exposed in real time to weather (top image) and underwater (bottom image) for three years and their degradation pathways and rates measured.

Conclusion

Plastics have revolutionized our daily lives in the fields of technology, medicine, clothing, food preservation, sport, art and more. However, no organic materials—including humans!—retain their original properties or functions forever. One major difference between plastics and other materials such as metals, ceramics and stone are their significantly shorter useable lifetimes. The challenges raised by the degradation of plastics in museums were recognized formally in 1991 largely inspired by the international conference ‘Saving the Twentieth Century: The Conservation of Modern Materials’. Concerns raised at the conference, and subsequent discussions and research resulted in the development of novel techniques to prolong the lifetimes of plastic artefacts and artworks (Grattan 1993). The formal identification of microplastics in the marine environment took place in 2004 and initiated a dramatic increase in research into the origins and impacts of these particles (Thompson et al. 2004).

More than thirty years after the degradation of plastics was recognized and acted upon in museums and twenty years after microplastics were first discovered on a beach in the UK, the first evidence of microplastic contamination in archaeological sediments was published (Rotchell et al. 2024). Almost simultaneously, the terms ‘wicked’ and ‘toxic’ became associated with plastics and cultural heritage. However, to date, no scientific research has shown that microplastics have interacted chemically or physically with archaeological materials or damaged archaeological sites. Based on the three examples of different types of plastics discussed here, plastics have contributed much to our technological development. They continue to impact our collections and our professional practices in both positive and negative ways. While concerns regarding the roles and impacts of different types of plastics are valid, interesting and certainly worth continued scrutiny, I would argue that it is too soon for archaeology to simply cancel them.

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Project Overview

Withstanding change: Bayt Al Jaghbeer and As-Salt's Role in Regional Resilience

Zeina Khashashneh

Petra National Trust

PETRA NATIONAL TRUST

الجمعية الوطنية للمحافظة على البترا

Figure 23. Petra National Trust logo.

As climate change increasingly threatens cultural heritage sites across the globe, local initiatives are emerging to safeguard cultural assets through sustainable practices. Bayt Al Jaghbeer, a historic house in As-Salt, Jordan, stands as a beacon of heritage preservation intertwined with community engagement and climate resilience. This contribution explores how Bayt Al Jaghbeer's restoration and educational programs address the dual challenges of heritage preservation and environmental change.

About Petra National Trust (PNT)

Petra National Trust (PNT) is a non-governmental, non-profit organization established in 1989 as Jordan's leading pioneer in cultural heritage conservation and preservation. See Figure 23. When first established, PNT focused on the UNESCO World Heritage site of Petra. Three decades later, PNT has become a regional centre of excellence in cultural heritage protection and has grown to offer heritage protection solutions and services across the Middle East and North Africa (MENA). HRH Princess Dana Firas, president of Petra National Trust and UNESCO Goodwill Ambassador for Cultural Heritage, oversees the implementation of PNT's mission and the fulfilment of its vision.

The Significance of Bayt Al Jaghbeer

Located at Khader Street, one of the key heritage areas in As-Salt, Bayt Al Jaghbeer is a prominent historical building known for its distinctive spatial layout, elaborate decorations, and authentic preservation over the years. See Figure 24. The house exemplifies As-Salt's transformation from a rural village to a thriving merchant town between the late 19th and early 20th centuries, showcasing unique stone textures, intricate stair formations and a blend of local and regional architectural influences. As-Salt's broader architectural landscape reflects a unique fusion of tribal traditions and influences from migrating merchants, reinforcing the city's identity as a center of tolerance and cohabitation.

Figure 24. The facade of Bayt Al Jaghbeer, a heritage house in As-Salt, Jordan, reflects the enduring legacy of traditional Levantine architecture. Built from As-Salt's characteristic yellow limestone, the structure features ornate arches and decorative elements emblematic of the late Ottoman period. These details stand as a testament to the craftsmanship and cultural identity that shaped the region's urban landscape.

Climate Change and Cultural Heritage

The ongoing restoration of Bayt Al Jaghbeer stands as a testament to the commitment to safeguarding Jordan's cultural heritage. This initiative began with extensive documentation and preservation planning, involving detailed assessments to record the house's current condition. Such efforts laid the

groundwork for a comprehensive rehabilitation process designed to ensure the site’s structural stability and longevity while respecting its historical authenticity.

Rehabilitation efforts have focused on revitalizing the building’s core infrastructure and mitigating environmental risks. A major milestone has been the environmental cleaning of interior spaces, where invasive weeds, limescale, and accumulated waste were cleared to prevent further deterioration. Simultaneously, roof restoration and structural reinforcement were prioritized to stabilize key architectural elements.

To address vulnerabilities posed by water damage, the project incorporated the installation of rainwater drainage systems and gutters. The original drainage plan underwent significant revision to prevent potential harm to the inner façade, reflecting the project’s attention to preserving the integrity of the structure. Courtyard stairs and selected walls have been carefully reconstructed using yellow stones sourced to match the original materials, ensuring that the building’s historic character remains intact.

An essential aspect of the restoration has been the revealing of the original flooring on the ground floor. See Figures 25-27. Layers of clay, debris, and additional materials were removed, allowing for the restoration and leveling of the surface. Where the original tiles were no longer present, the courtyard will be tiled with terracotta pieces crafted from As-Salt clay, blending traditional craftsmanship with preservation needs.

Figure 25. The first-floor courtyard of Bayt Al Jaghbeer exemplifies the charm and functionality of late Ottoman-period homes. Encircled by elegant arches and constructed from the iconic yellow limestone of As-Salt, the courtyard serves as the heart of the residence, fostering light, ventilation, and social gatherings. The layered stonework and staircases reflect the craftsmanship of the period, while the open-air design highlights the seamless blend between private and communal spaces in traditional Levantine architecture.

Figure 26. A unique and striking example of late Ottoman craftsmanship, these spiral stone stairs at Bayt Al Jaghbeer connect the first floor to the upper level. The staircase’s vaulted arch and hand-carved steps reflect the ingenuity of traditional architecture, seamlessly blending form and function in this heritage house.

As part of securing the site, a temporary wooden door replaced a cement block barrier, while a permanent metal door inspired by the original design is currently under development.

Bayt Al Jaghbeer, like many heritage sites in Jordan, faces growing environmental challenges, including rising temperatures, fluctuations in precipitation, and increased humidity—factors that accelerate

structural decay. The restoration project integrates adaptive strategies drawn from traditional practices, such as utilizing local materials and enhancing drainage systems, while addressing modern issues like rising damp and chemical efflorescence. This initiative reflects a broader national effort to align cultural preservation with environmental sustainability, reinforcing Jordan's commitment to climate adaptation policies and the protection of its rich architectural legacy.

Figure 27. Restoration work within the ground-floor courtyard of Bayt Al Jaghbeer highlights the contrast between the original stone stairs and the newly added elements, reflecting careful intervention to preserve the house's cultural character. Bayt Al Jaghbeer stands out as one of the few heritage houses in As-Salt with two courtyards, a rare architectural feature that enhances its significance. This central space, framed by grand arches and stone staircases, plays a vital role in the preservation efforts aimed at safeguarding the site's integrity while reviving its function as a vibrant community and cultural hub.

Community and Cross-Regional Collaboration

Bayt Al Jaghbeer's restoration was implemented by PNT and supported by the International National Trusts Organization (INTO) in funding from the British Council's Cultural Protection Fund to support climate-related heritage activities across the Middle East and Africa. As part of this initiative, INTO's 'Withstanding Change' project is currently restoring six historic sites threatened by climate change, including Bayt Al Jaghbeer. This international collaboration fosters knowledge exchange and strengthens climate resilience strategies across the region.

Educational Initiatives and Youth Engagement

In the face of mounting environmental challenges, the Petra National Trust (PNT) has launched a series of forward-looking programs aimed at preserving Jordan’s cultural heritage while equipping youth with the tools to combat climate change. Through comprehensive educational initiatives and hands-on restoration training, PNT continues to foster a generation of leaders committed to sustainable development and heritage conservation.

The Climate Heritage Youth Leaders Program stands out as a flagship initiative, addressing the pressing threats that climate change poses to both biodiversity and cultural heritage. Designed for participants aged 16 to 18 and 18+, the program educates youth on sustainable development practices, encouraging them to become advocates for heritage preservation. The curriculum was developed in phases, beginning with in-depth research on the effects of climate change on cultural sites. Key components include a structured trainer’s guide, trainee handbooks, and interactive presentations that combined theory with practical application. Participants were carefully selected from over 100 applicants. 54 young leaders were ultimately chosen for two workshops held in As-Salt. See Figure 28. These workshops combined classroom learning with field visits to Al-Shumari Wildlife and Azraq Wetland Reserves (See Figure 29), immersing participants in local ecosystems to highlight the links between natural and cultural heritage. Practical activities such as ecosystem diorama creation and recycling crafts reinforced lessons on environmental responsibility.

Figure 28. Climate Heritage Youth Leaders participants engaging in a hands-on workshop, collaborating to craft a diorama for a cultural heritage site in Jordan using clay. The activity reflects their understanding to preserving heritage and addressing climate change challenges.

PNT's Twinning Program with the National Trust represents another pillar of cultural exchange and collaboration. Recent discussions with representatives from Coleshill have paved the way for a knowledge-sharing initiative, with a focus on community engagement and youth education. This partnership aims to strengthen the ties between local heritage initiatives in Jordan and global preservation efforts.

In parallel, restoration training has been central to PNT's preservation strategy. A comprehensive training course on heritage resource management brought together 27 participants from diverse academic backgrounds. The program combined lectures, site visits, and hands-on demonstrations, offering participants practical skills in restoration techniques such as surface cleaning, stone treatment, and structural reinforcement.

Figure 29. Exploring the impact of climate change firsthand: Participants of the Climate Heritage Youth Leaders Program visit the Azraq Wetland Reserve to observe and understand the environmental challenges affecting this vital ecosystem. This visit emphasizes the importance of youth engagement in heritage and climate action. The restoration training not only increased awareness of the risks climate change poses to heritage sites, but also equipped participants with the expertise to apply adaptive restoration strategies, such as shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30. Empowering heritage preservation through hands-on training: A dedicated female participant engages in restoration techniques, utilizing local materials to safeguard cultural landmarks. This highlights the importance of traditional knowledge in maintaining our shared history while promoting inclusivity and skill development in the field of conservation.

PNT's commitment to heritage preservation extends to public engagement through exhibitions and conferences. An exhibition hosted in December 2024 (Facing Change Conference- Jordan 2024) spotlighted the use of natural restoration materials such as mud and their vulnerability to climate change. Experts have presented the resilience and challenges of these materials, fostering international dialogue on sustainable restoration practices.

Through these interconnected initiatives, PNT continues to lead the charge in protecting Jordan's cultural heritage while empowering future generations to play an active role in preserving the past for a sustainable future. Bayt Al Jaghbeer stands as a compelling case study in how heritage sites can adapt to and mitigate the impacts of climate change. Its restoration underscores the

interconnectedness of cultural preservation, environmental sustainability and community engagement. As the climate crisis intensifies, such initiatives provide valuable lessons for heritage conservation that may be successfully implemented worldwide, positioning As-Salt as a leader in climate-resilient cultural heritage preservation.

Project Overview

Heritage in Action: Grassroots Preservation and Youth Education with The Kru Coast Heritage Initiative in Liberia, West Africa

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“Until lions have their own historians, the story of the hunt will be told by the hunter.”

Commonly cited as a West African proverb, the quotation given above is the motto of the Kru Coast Heritage Initiative (KCHI). The Kru Coast Heritage Initiative is a grassroots community research project based in Greenville, Sinoe County, Liberia that aims to bring out the history, archaeology and heritage of the Kru (Krao) people in the southeastern region of Liberia. See Figure 31. Our project is a collaboration between researchers, students, elders and teachers that documents, records, preserves and analyzes historical and archaeological data about the Kru (one among Liberia’s 16 recognized Indigenous groups) in their own words. This article highlights the recent efforts of the initiative to foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of Liberian history, including an upcoming heritage workshop for high school students that seeks to connect youth with critical thinking tools and historical fieldwork.

The Kru are one Indigenous group in Liberia who achieved relative fame in global history because of their capacity to work as sailors on different European ships as early as the fifteenth century AD. Oral history accounts recorded by our project suggest that the Kru (and other related groups) began migrations south from Mali as early as the 14th century (Gunn 2021: 9; Nagbe 2023). Upon settling on the Liberian and Ivoirian coasts, the Kru took up fishing, farming, portage, boatbuilding, contract sailing and global trade brokerage, activities in which many individuals continue to be engaged to the present day. They worked especially closely with the British during the seventeenth to nineteenth centuries, even going as far as petitioning the League of Nations in the early 20th century to be separated from Liberia and incorporated into British West Africa.

The histories of the Kru Indigenous people have most often been told using European archival documents, which are understandably biased toward Eurocentric interpretations of this history. While several authors have written about Kru maritime history and other aspects of Kru sociopolitical history (Breitborde 1991; Brooks 1972; Crutcher 2023; Davis 1976; Fraenkel 1966; Frost 1999; Gunn 2021; Martin 1985; Massing 1980; McEvoy 1977; Mekeel 1937; Moran 1986, 1988; Sullivan 1978; Tonkin 1995), systematic research into local archaeology and oral histories have not been conducted in the

Kru ancestral land of Sinoe County since at least before the Liberian Civil Wars. The KCHI project seeks to remedy this situation through local historic preservation and archaeological research.

Figure 31. A map of Liberia showing the entire country (top left), Sinoe County with major districts (top right), and the coastal region in which the project operates (bottom). Image by the authors.

Liberia has an interesting place in the history of West Africa and colonization. It was never officially colonized by Europeans but was settled during the nineteenth century by formerly enslaved people from the U.S. and Caribbean. Many of the settlers were caught between opposing interests; on the one hand, they were not too interested in leaving behind their families and ways of life in the U.S. to migrate to uncertain shores. Many prominent Black intellectuals opposed the colonization movement: in 1849, Frederick Douglass wrote to the Rochester *North Star* that “the mean and cowardly oppressor is meditating plans to expel the coloured man entirely from the country [the U.S.]. Shame upon the guilty wretches that dare propose, and all that countenance such a proposition. We live here—have lived here—have a right to live here, and mean to live here” (Douglass 1849). On the other hand, slaveholders in the U.S. saw the growing population of free African Americans as a threat to white supremacy, and so they forced many settlers to choose between remaining enslaved in the U.S. or emigrating in exchange for their freedom from slavery.

The settlers who did choose to emigrate took up farming and maritime trade in their settlements on the Liberian coast. Those settlers made use of tactics like obtuse treaties and misunderstood concepts

of land ownership to expand their territory against Indigenous Liberians like the Kru. The settlers also found themselves constantly trying to prove U.S. pro-colonization racist prejudices wrong by showing that people of African descent could govern themselves and advance what was considered by white American elites to be ‘civilized’ society. Liberia became a beacon of Black citizenship and liberation across the Black Atlantic, even as Indigenous rights were often disregarded. Indigenous Liberians were seen neither as ‘civilized’ nor as citizens until a 1946 constitutional amendment enshrined their right to vote. The Kru were especially vocal about their treatment by the settler populations in southeastern Sinoe County. After a century of fraught relationships with the settlers around Greenville, the Kru people had become dissatisfied with the situation, so they wrote to what was then the newly-formed League of Nations, asking the League to intervene. Throughout the 1910s until the 1930s, Kru chiefs petitioned the League of Nations, the U.S. government and the government of British West Africa to intervene in their affairs—to no avail. During this period, there were several wars between the government of Liberia and the Kru people. It was only by the early 1940s that the Kru territory was incorporated into the nation of Liberia. Many of these tensions and violence between Indigenous people and anyone associated with the settlers were exploited in the 1980 coup that toppled settler rule and in the 1989-2003 Liberian Civil Wars that killed more than a quarter of the population. While peace has come to Liberia and the country has been democratic and stable since 2005, many are still searching for reconciliation, justice and honesty. History has a large role to play in connecting people to the past and seeking to understand those events that took place so that they will not be repeated.

Our project emphasizes Indigenous and Kru Liberian history because we believe that knowing the past can help us understand the present and prepare for the future. It is easy to blame the Liberian settlers for the oppression of the Indigenous people without understanding their difficult situation and the racism and violence they themselves faced in the U.S. This does not absolve them of the acts they committed during the first hundred years of Liberian history, but it helps us form a deep and nuanced historical understanding that can help us build peace, reconciliation and collaboration across boundaries and backgrounds in the present.

Since 2023, the Kru Coast Heritage Initiative team has been recording oral histories and conducting archaeological survey across Sinoe County with the aim of preserving historical memory in an often-overlooked region of Liberia. Our project has recorded and transcribed more than 20 oral history interviews and excavated over 986 artefacts across 12 contexts in Settra Kru (Welteh), the oldest known Indigenous port in Sinoe County. Some of these artefacts are pictured in Figure 32. We aim to grow our initiative towards supporting historical education, critical thinking and community discussion so that interested persons—especially youth and elders—can benefit from these historical topics.

Our research began with a door-to-door campaign of oral history interviews of local elders. We started in Greenville (Snoklee) and interviewed elders from almost every village throughout the region up to the Lower Tartweh Chiefdom. The Kru tribe is divided into 48 sections, and each section has its own history. The Tartweh are one of the largest sections on the interior side. We ended up at Settra Kru (Welteh), the port mentioned previously. Settra Kru is a small town in the coastal region of the Kru tribe and also the focus point of our archaeological investigations. The interviewees there welcomed the idea of recording their oral histories. All interviewees provided the side of the history they were told by their forefathers; some of the information with which we were provided addressed the origin of the Kru people, their livelihoods, and those activities in which they were involved before the arrival of African-American and Afro-Caribbean settlers.

Figure 32. Artefacts excavated at the site of Settra Kru. Images by the authors.

We also conducted public archaeology in Settra Kru. See Figure 33. The artefacts we excavated point to a long period of maritime trade and exchange in the area. The Kru established and sustained global trading relationships as evidenced by historical documents and by the material remains of exchange that first allowed them to assert economic, political and social independence from colonization by Europeans like the Portuguese, and later allowed them to challenge settler colonization during the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. Part of Liberia’s claim of being the first Black Republic and never having been colonized by Europeans is due to the resistance of the Kru before African-American and Afro-Caribbean settlement in the nineteenth century.

Figure 33. Conducting community archaeology with youth and children from Settra Kru. Photo by the authors.

We are currently working with 20 students from various senior high schools in Greenville, and we are trying to document the history of the Kru people by doing interviews and recording the memories of elderly people whose memories and lived experiences make up a dwindling historical resource. Our methods include making recordings of oral historical accounts, which is very important for the next generation. The students are eager to participate because many of them are Indigenous and they see that Indigenous people, especially the Kru people, are very special when it comes to African and West African history.

Our aim in incorporating these students is to teach them how to make oral history recordings and to then document the recording in writing through transcription and indexing. We are teaching them about the use of the scientific method to answer historical questions by comparing different accounts and analyzing data that they will gather. They will also learn to do archaeology so that they can understand or get a clearer picture of some of the materials we have excavated. They will be able to recognize the importance and value of archaeological materials and the need for their preservation, analysis, and continued protection. These materials include coarse earthenware (referred to in Liberia as “country pots”), tobacco pipes that were traded in this area by the Europeans, blacksmithing materials and cooking utensils, among other things. As the first archaeological investigation in the southeastern region of Liberia, our project is building a sustainable solution that places the responsibility for understanding and protecting archaeological materials in the hands of the community, rather than in the hands of outside researchers from the Global North. All of the project materials will stay in Liberia in perpetuity.

We developed and distributed workbooks as a teaching tool and research resource to the students. The workbooks instruct students in primary source analysis, oral history interviewing, and some of the major historiographical trends in Kru history. The primary sources come from the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries and detail some of the struggles that the Kru faced in their self-determination and economic independence. In the workbook, some of the things that are highlighted are the founding of Liberia, the reason for the founding of Liberia, the histories of Indigenous Liberians, and the role of the international communities during more recent Liberian history.

In the ongoing workshop, we also talk about the histories of Indigenous people in Liberia and how the settler government often treated them. See Figure 34. The primary sources that we read challenged the idea that the Indigenous people were uneducated or ‘primitive,’ which is how many students are still taught about their own culture in school (Lissa et al., 2024). We concluded the first workshop by taking a walk from the Samuel Morris Center in Greenville (where our project is headquartered) to the end of Mississippi Street, one of the historic streets in the city of Greenville. This historic street is currently being worn away by the waves of the Atlantic Ocean. By discussing Kru history and then visiting these important sites, we are connecting our study of the past with present and future issues faced by Indigenous Liberians, such as climate change, sea level rise and coastal erosion (Crutcher and Kondeh 2024). Students were given the opportunity to discuss some of the pressing issues that they identify from their own experiences growing up in this region, such as the importance of historic preservation and remembering the past.

Figure 34. Prince Kondeh leads a workshop with Sinoe County high school students. Photo by the authors.

By engaging local communities (especially youth) in the process of documenting and analyzing their history, the Kru Coast Heritage Initiative ensures that the historical memory of Kru elders and other important members of the Kru tribe are not lost to time. This project empowers future generations to continue the work of preservation and reconciliation in a nation with one of the fastest growing youth populations in the world. Our team works together to facilitate preservation and conversation about Indigenous Liberian history in the southeastern region.

To learn more about the Kru Coast Heritage Initiative, find us online at www.krucoastheritage.weebly.com or on Facebook under the page “Kru/Krao coast heritage initiative.”

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Community Spotlight

Community for Climate Change and Heritage (CCH)

Vibeke Vandrup Martens, Peter F. Biehl and Mairi Davies

Community Chairs

After several years of organizing sessions both at the EAA as well as at the Society for American Archaeology (SAA) on the archaeology of climate change, *in situ* site preservation, and on the impact of climate change on heritage preservation, the Community for Climate Change and Heritage (CCH) was founded by Peter F Biehl, Elin Dalen and Vibeke Vandrup Martens in 2017. The three acted as joint community leaders, attended community assemblies and arranged yearly round table sessions. In parallel, they arranged and presented at sessions on the same and related topics to increase awareness and to work towards best practices to benefit the broader community and society. The roundtable sessions always gathered large audiences, and the community has a steadily growing number of members.

In 2021, the CCH joint forces with [SACC](#) (Social Archaeology of Climate Change) at the Kiel EAA meeting to enhance the focus on how archaeology and historic knowledge may contribute to combatting or remediating modern day climate change impacts, and was actively involved in drafting the [2021 EAA Statement on Archaeology and Climate Change](#).

At the EAA in Budapest in 2022, Elin Dalen stepped down from the CCH leadership and Mairi Davies from Historic Environment Scotland joined the leadership. At the last CCH roundtable in Rome (2024) it was decided to send a survey to all CCH community members to identify with them both opportunities and challenges for the future direction and impact of the CCH community.

We see many opportunities for further future work, including practical implementations of adaptation or mitigation measures, research on impacts and solutions and working with local communities and across borders. We are applying for research grants to gain further knowledge and work towards finding new ways of documenting and communicating about cultural heritage both separately and jointly. We also see opportunities for working more with other EAA Communities, such as Heritage and Tourism (e.g. a possible joint excursion during the EAA Annual Meeting in Belgrade), a joint session

with many of the other Communities, and generally contributing to highlight the positive contributions of archaeology and heritage to society.

Finding the best local solutions to the global challenge of climate change can be demanding, and in many cases adaptation or documentation can only be carried out at great cost. That sends a signal that only the past of well-to-do countries is important – and that is certainly not true! We need to preserve and document all our joint history and heritage on a global scale. This may require altruistic work or redistribution of funds, but first and foremost it does require funding. Cultural heritage is far from the level of funding attributed to the preservation of natural heritage, but we see that as an opportunity of even broader cooperation (and a worthy challenge).

The CCH works closely with the Society for American Archaeology committee on Climate Change Strategies and Archaeological Resources (SAA CCSAR), through first Biehl and subsequently Martens represented both CCH and CCSAR and through attendance and presentations at sessions at both conferences, as well as giving input to the SAA statement on climate change and archaeological resources in 2021. We have also had strong attendance and arranged sessions at the World Archaeological Conference (WAC) and presented at the Shanghai Archaeology Conference. Davies works with the CVI (Climate Vulnerability Index) for World Heritage Sites and has done a lot of international work through that engagement. Obviously, we work with the Climate-Heritage group, with the Union of Concerned Scientists, with North American Heritage at Risk (NAHAR) and many others. The coming issue of *Journal of Field Archaeology* (JFA 50 (1)) will also be dedicated exclusively to the topic of climate change and heritage as a direct result of a session at the 2022 World Archaeological Congress in Prague.

We believe that further development of new documentation and digital preservation methods as well as environmental monitoring, the further development of adaptation measures and the implementation of historical means of dealing with the impacts of climate change will all play important roles in the future of archaeology and heritage management. We strongly believe that saving information of our common past will help people enjoy life in the present and shape the future.

Climate change is a global problem. However, to ensure global heritage preservation and protection, we need locally-adapted solutions. We also need to look for affordable ways to preserve and communicate our past, either in place or digitally. We encourage current members to spread the word among their networks to [join the CCH](#) and complete the CCH survey in 2025!

In Memoriam

Françoise Audouze

Françoise Audouze, 1943 – 2024. Photo from Canal U/UMR Temps.

Our colleague the French prehistorian Françoise Audouze passed away on 12 August 2024. A member of the EAA Executive Board from 1997 to 2003, she was in charge of the organisation of the EAA's 10th annual meeting in Lyon in 2004, the only time to date that EAA meetings were held in France. Together with Jacques Lasfargue, director of the Rhône-Alpes regional archaeological service, she ensured that the conference unfolded in excellent conditions, taking advantage of the venerable archaeological history of Lyon, the capital of Gaul in Roman times.

Born in 1943, Françoise Audouze studied prehistory at the Sorbonne with André Leroi-Gourhan, the most innovative French prehistorian of his time. Her first interest was in the Bronze Age, of which there were at that time very few specialists in France: following her thesis on this topic, she was recruited by the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS). In addition to her own research, she took part in two major surveys of Bronze Age artefacts, the *Prähistorische Bronzefunde*, coordinated by Hermann Müller-Karpe in Germany, and the series *typologies de l'âge du Bronze en France*, launched by the *Société préhistorique française*. And it was on this same subject that she taught from 1975 to 2000 at the University of Paris I Panthéon-Sorbonne, so as to broaden the protohistory curricula from its main focus on the Neolithic and Iron Age periods. The seminar she later taught in Nanterre on “the archaeology of technology” (with Sander van der Leeuw and Nathan Schlanger) did much to strengthen the interdisciplinary character and the theoretical ambitions of the study of techniques, *à la française*. In this respect, her 2002 article on “Leroi-Gourhan, a Philosopher

of Technique and Evolution” proved influential in presenting the thrust of this research tradition to an English-reading scholarly audience.

Such initiatives helped considerably to disprove the label of “continental insularity” long stuck, with considerable justification, to French archaeology. Indeed, Françoise played an active role in modernising French archaeology, which had a venerable tradition of research in the Mediterranean “cradles of civilisation” in Greece, Italy, the Near East and Egypt, but which remained for long underdeveloped on French soil. There, even as late as the 1970s, most archaeological excavations were carried out by enthusiastic amateurs, with only limited resources, uncertain professional standards and loose legal frameworks. In 1979, together with Anick Coudart, Alain Schnapp and Jean-Paul Demoule, among others, Françoise was one of the founders of the militant journal *Les Nouvelles de l'Archéologie*, which played a key role in mobilising French archaeologists and in bringing about a number of essential scientific and organisational reforms, including the proper establishment of preventive archaeology as a research oriented public service. From 1987 to 1998, she also took on the direction of the CNRS archaeological research centre at Valbonne near Nice, which federated a network of some twenty teams spread across France.

While Françoise initially undertook several archaeological digs on Bronze and Iron Age sites, her main excavation project, lasting from 1976 until 2009, was at Verberie, a major Magdalenian settlement on the banks of the River Oise. She extended there the methodologies developed by Leroi-Gourhan at the famous Upper Palaeolithic site of Pincevent, particularly with regards to environmental sciences, studies of seasonality, fauna and spatial analysis, the whole resulting in numerous publications. In addition to her European connections, Françoise had also many scientific links with women researchers in the United States, and shared their interests in questions of gender and the archaeology of childhood. She took an active part in the annual meetings of the Society for American Archaeology and taught at the University of Illinois and the University of California in 1997 and 1998.

In recent years, before her health declined, she set to complete the research and publication of the data accumulated from her excavations at Verberie, but she also found the time to support an NGO in Bangladesh. She will be sorely missed for her spirit, at once incisive and open-minded, as well as the encouragements she knew to give to students and younger colleagues, in France and abroad.

Jean-Paul Demoule & Nathan Schlanger

Colin Renfrew

Colin Renfrew, 1937-2024. Photo taken 2018 from treasure Valuation Committee; image CCBY2.0 by Portable Antiquities Scheme.

The tallest tree in the forest of great European archaeologists has fallen. The death of Colin Renfrew marks the end of an archaeological period that he was central in shaping: the transformation of archaeology from a dominantly empirical discipline avoiding theory, to a theoretically informed science that put interpretation and comparative models from social anthropology at the forefront. By employing advances of the second science revolution in C14 dates combined with new environmental evidence, he redefined European prehistory, as summarized in his 1973 book *Before Civilization*.

Here, however, I shall concentrate on his importance in the formation of the EAA, and the inaugural conference in Ljubljana, which coincided with the opening the Council of Europe's Bronze Age Campaign: 'The First Golden Age of Europe'. These threads became intertwined, and I shall recall the travels that led up to this.

But before that there were the long years of preparing what would become the EAA. When we formed the working group that would prepare the formation of EAA around 1988, I asked Colin Renfrew to join. He accepted, as he supported the purpose, but he also made clear that he could not take part in meetings. However, his support had an important impact, and I could always consult him (which I did a few times, to get his advice or support in particular cases).

We were ready to launch the EAA inaugural meeting in Ljubljana in September 1994. However, a few days before that the Council of Europe launched its European Archaeology Campaign on the Bronze Age. Colin also participated in that, and he held the opening speech in Vienna, after which we were all put on a river boat sailing down the Danube, making stops in Bratislava to open an exhibition, and ending in Budapest, where another exhibition opened. Willem Willems has vividly described these events: 'At the end of the 3-day boat trip, on Wednesday 21 September, we – I remember the entire Kristiansen family and Colin Renfrew – were taken by a van that the efficient Predag Novakovic had sent for us from the Danube to Ljubljana, making some detour to avoid Croatia where the war was going on. The inaugural meeting went well, with Colin as a kind of European archaeological godfather presenting a memorable inaugural address.'

Figure 35. Kristiansen interviews Renfrew at the opening ceremony of the 25th annual EAA AM in Bern. Photo courtesy of Kristian Kristiansen.

Figure 36. Renfrew and Lotte Hedeager dancing at a previous Annual Party in the Haag to music played by Kristian Kristiansen and band. Photo courtesy of Kristian Kristiansen.

This, however, was not the end of Colin's engagement with the EAA. Colin was heavily engaged in tracing and documenting illicit trade in archaeological antiquities, and to support that he had created a research centre at Cambridge's McDonald Institute. This work was rewarded when the EAA heritage prize in 2004 was presented to his 'Illicit Antiquities Research Centre' after which Colin presented an engaged and merciless opening lecture on the subject. I remember especially how he exposed well-known museums for their participation in such trade. This bold and critical side of Colin's work deserves to be commemorated, especially as the Illicit Antiquities Research Centre was closed shortly after his retirement.

Colin's final active engagement with the EAA took place at the celebration of its 25th anniversary in Bern. The organizers had asked me to interview Colin at the opening ceremony, and he readily accepted. See Figure 35. I remember especially that he thought EAA had raised critical awareness of what European archaeology means (both good and bad), but also contrasted that with previous nationally-organized archaeology. At the following annual party, Colin again was active on the dance floor; his musical engagement was another side of his passionate life (Figure 36).

I will miss him, personally as a discussion partner, but most of all we should remember all he did to transform European archaeology into what it is today, and in the process his contribution to the birth of the EAA.

Kristian Kristiansen

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Announcements

Take part in the European Archaeology Days 2025!

The European Archaeology Days will take place on 13, 14 and 15 June 2023. How can you participate?

First of all, you need to come up with a line-up of specific activities for the EADs, taking care to fulfil a certain number of criteria: opening up the places where archaeology is done, furthering the interaction between archaeology professionals and the public, offering up different activities (i.e. a change from the usual programming) which appeal to those not familiar with archaeology, encouraging children and young people to participate and—in particular—by planning activities for families or school groups on Fridays.

The next step is to register and publish your program on the website (journees-archeologie.fr) via the organiser account you will have opened on the page for your country. **Registration will open on 17 February 2025.** To facilitate participation in the EADs, we provide communication tools for the organisers, which they can download via their account. We also provide a ‘Guide for Event Organisers’ to help you put together and create awareness about your programme. Should you have questions, you are welcome to contact Pascal Ratier at pascal.ratier@inrap.fr.

open call

BeFRAIL Webinar Series 2025

For the second edition of the BeFRAIL webinar series we would like to extend an open call for contributions, in addition to the programme of invited speakers that we are currently composing.

This year the webinar series will focus on exploring ethical considerations and social impacts in Bioarchaeology and Biological Anthropology.

We particularly want to encourage early career researchers, including Masters and PhD students and recent graduates, to reach out if you would like to share your research and its ethical and social dimensions. Please contact BeFRAIL@fcsch.unl.pt until **February 17th** in order to submit your proposal. Talks will be 15 minutes long with 5 minutes for questions.

